

**Performance of Precipitation Products on Rainfall Runoff Modeling in
Koshi Basin**

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Abbreviation and acronyms

ANNs	Artificial Neural Networks
APHRODITE	Asian Precipitation - Highly-Resolved Observational Data Integration towards Evaluation
CMA	China Meteorological Administration
CMORPH	Climate Prediction Center Morphing Technique
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DHM	Department of Hydrology and Meteorology
GSMaP	Global Satellite Mapping of Precipitation
HIMS	Hydro informatics Modeling System
HRU	Hydrological Response Unit
HWSD	Harmonized World Soil Database
IPWG	International Precipitation Working Group
JAMS	Jena Adaptable Modelling System
NCVST	Nepal Climate Vulnerability Study Team
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's
NSE	Nash Sutcliffe Efficiency
PERSIANN	Precipitation Estimation from Remote Sensing Information using artificial Neural Network
PMW	Passive Microwave
RBIS	River Basin Information System
RFE	Rainfall Estimate
SPPs	Satellite Based Precipitation Products
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
SWAT	Soil and Water Assessment Tool
TLR	Temperature Lapse Rate
TRMM	Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission
VIC	Variable Infiltration Capacity

Abstract

Precipitation is a vital component of the hydrological process and key essential meteorological inputs of hydrologic model. In high Himalayan, remote regions and mountainous areas, rain gauges and meteorological radar networks are either sparse or non-existent. Thus, satellite-based precipitation is of great importance in such regions. Errors in precipitation estimation can bring significant uncertainties in stream flow simulation and prediction. The precipitation estimation in the complex geographical region, Himalayas and mountain are always on the question mark, even though it has high temporal and spatial resolution. To address such issues, this study focus on the evaluation of gauge and Satellite Based Precipitation Products (SPPs) such as Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM), Asian Precipitation - Highly-Resolved Observational Data Integration towards Evaluation (Aphrodite), Multi-Source Weighted-Ensemble Precipitation (MSWEP) and Climate Prediction Center Morphing Technique (CMORPH) on J2000 rainfall-runoff model in Koshi basin that lies at Tibetan and Nepal part. Different input data set such as rain, temperature, wind, sunshine duration, relative humidity and parameter files such as Hydrological Response Units (HRUs), reaches, soil, land use, geology are collected from different sources or developed using different tools such as Arc GIS, QGIS, Hydrus1D.4xx, Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD) viewer, R and Python script for model initialization. A total 12,661 units of HRUs and 342 reaches are delineated which represented the spatial heterogeneity of the basin. Two methods are employed to evaluate the precipitation products on J2000 model. In the method I, the model is calibrated based on gauge precipitation as the main input and other precipitation products are evaluated based on gauge calibration parameter and method II involve the individual calibration of precipitation products as the main input and the performance are carried out simultaneously.

Under the method I, the statistical performance shows that gauge has the highest Nash Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) of 0.78 and lowest Relative Percentage Volume Error (PBIAS) of -0.11% which is followed by Aphrodite, TRMM, MSWEP and CMORPH respectively. Under the method II, the difference between observed and simulated discharge values are considerably reduced, resulting in improved model efficiency. The products Aphrodite, TRMM, MSWEP and CMORPH have increased NSE values from (0.68 to 0.77), (0.62 to 0.69), (0.20 to 0.40) and (0.08 to 0.18) respectively and decreased values of PBIAS from (22.40 to -7.93%), (5.32 to 0.98) %, (67.30 to 51.84) % and (-75.83 to -52.98) % respectively. The 17 year average observed peak flood occur at 20 August with the corresponding discharge of $4,757 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and yearly analysis shows that peak flood occur in the days of July and August. The timing of flood peaks of gauge, TRMM and Aphrodite nearly match the observed discharge timing based on the yearly analysis. The average lead or lag timing for gauge, Aphrodite, MSWEP, TRMM and CMORPH under method I have the average value of 6.8, 11.5, 16.6, 15.6 and 18.1 days respectively which is similar to method II. The ranking of precipitation products under the method I, has the gauge as 1st rank followed by TRMM in 2nd rank, Aphrodite in 3rd rank, MSWEP in 4th rank and CMORPH in the last rank. Under the method II, the Aphrodite is rank as 1st, TRMM as 2nd, MSWEP as 3rd and CMORPH as last rank.

This study gives clear views that simulation discharges from gauge nearly matches, Aphrodite slightly underestimate, MSWEP highly overestimates, TRMM slightly overestimates and CMORPH highly underestimates than observed discharge. The TRMM and MSWEP after bias correction may be used for flood modeling and Aphrodite products can be used for water balance estimation where there is the unavailability of rain gauge, complex geographical condition and place where the establishment of rain gauge is not economically feasible. However, there are some issues on data scarcity and study limitation on soil depth, land-cover and model uncertainty. It is recommended to establish gauge station in such geographical area for proper representation of rainfall from the whole basin, soil depth mapping and model uncertainty analysis. So, this study may give the clear overview on documenting and verifying historical incidents such as droughts and flood event that take place in the complex terrain of an area like country Nepal in order to save life and property.

Keywords: model parameter, discharge simulation, flood peak, lead-lag time, ranking,

Chapter I

1 Introduction

Precipitation is the vital component of the hydrological process and key essential meteorological inputs of hydrologic model. Understanding on precipitation helps to predict the total runoff in the basin. The large volume of runoff flood in downstream effect the life and properties and accurate estimation reduce the loss into substantial amount with increasing lead time. Three methods are generally used to measure precipitation: traditional ground gauge observations, meteorological radar observations, and satellite observations (Ashouri *et al.*, 2015). In-ground level it is done with ground gauging station and to get an accurate estimation of precipitation for basin area, the network of ground gauging station should be placed close together with the definite number within the fixed area. In developing countries and most populated region of the world, the gauging stations are spare in temporal and spatial distribution or may not be existed (Kidd *et al.*, 2009). This situation is created due to the complex geographical region or expensive network set up or both of them (Tamrakar, 2011). The main challenge in developing countries is an estimation of accurate precipitation from the ground gauge might be insufficient information for the water-related development project in such area.

Satellite precipitation plays a vital role when there is no rainfall station and coverage is lower. Errors in precipitation estimation can bring significant uncertainties in stream flow simulation and prediction (Sorooshian *et al.*, 2011). The main characteristics of satellite precipitation data are its areal distributed measurement and sampling error in representing average precipitation over an area through point measurement in ground gauging station (Tamrakar, 2011). In today's world various high spatial and temporal resolution satellites product are generated by combined use of infrared (IR) and passive microwave (PMW) observation from multiple satellites. These data can be obtained from various operational agencies and academic institution such as CPC MORPHing technique (CMORPH), Precipitation Estimation from Remote Sensing Information using Artificial Neural Network (PERSIANN), Rainfall Estimate (RFE) 2.0, Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM), Global Satellite Mapping of Precipitation (GSMaP) etc. Moreover, the ground data are used to calibrate the model and the satellite precipitation data and combination of these products gives the more reliable product (Shrestha, 2011).

1.1 Statement of problem

Precipitation in mountain regions is often highly variable and poorly observed, limiting abilities to manage water resource challenges (Krakauer *et al.*, 2013). These regions are more critical to regional water resource with often heavy downpour supplying water to extensive downstream reaches and are also vulnerable to hydrological hazard such as flooding (Viviroli *et al.*, 2007). It is more realistic in the case of Nepal where the freshwater resource directly depends upon the amount of precipitation (Duncan and Biggs, 2012), which could be altered under a future climate change. According to McDowell *et al.*

(2013) societies that live in and among the mountainous regions of developing countries are some of the most vulnerable to climate change.

Nepal is suffering from the various number of natural disasters like floods, landslide and avalanches every year due to its diverse geological conditions, rugged terrain with vast climatic variability within a short north-south distance (Shrestha and Chhophel, 2010). Water stress during the dry season and frequent floods during the monsoons are the biggest challenges in the Koshi basin (NCVST, 2009). Flood forecasting and flood early warning systems are one of the most effective ways to minimize the loss and damage. At the same time, more than 65% population of Nepal practiced subsistence agriculture which is highly water dependent (FAO, 2010) which also demands the accurate precipitation estimation in agricultural season. In high Himalayan, remote regions and mountainous areas, rain gauges and meteorological radar networks are either sparse or non-existent. Thus, satellite-based precipitation is of great importance in such regions. Accurate precipitation estimation can play a vital role to predict floods in the monsoon, water scarcity in the dry season, sedimentation and erosion in the river and associated floodplains, drainage congestion in the low lying areas, environmental and water quality issues.

1.2 Need for study and research gap

In the mountainous region of Nepal, the spatial distribution of precipitation greatly varies due to orographic and rain shadow effects caused by high hills, mountains and Himalayas are critical to assessing mountain water resources. So for accurate estimation of precipitation over the area, precipitation stations should be placed close together. To obtain the good result, substantial network of rain gauges or ground-based precipitation measuring radar are very important in real time. Department of Hydrology and Meteorology (DHM), which is the only responsible organization for hydrometeorological data acquisition and distribution, had installed one gauge for about 331 km² and it is even sparse in mountainous areas and data are available only after the significant delay (Lasiwa, 2016). One cost-effective alternative is to estimate rainfall using data from a combination of satellite sensors. But the estimate from the satellite observation contains errors and bias because of the indirect nature of the relationship between the observation and the precipitation, the inadequate sampling and algorithm imperfections (Xie *et al.*, 2002). Precise and accurate satellite-derived data are important for documenting and verifying historical incidents such as droughts and flood event that take place in the complex terrain of the area like country Nepal in order to save life and property. Reliable satellite products are the basis for active climatological monitoring of precipitation which is very much useful across the distributed population of extreme terrain. Accurate measurement of amount and intensity of precipitation play a significant role in assessing agricultural, geomorphic, and ecological impacts of precipitation events (Barros and Lang, 2003).

Although remote sensing precipitation products based on satellite observations offer potentially high spatial and temporal resolution and low latency, discrepancies between available products put their accuracy for mountain regions in question (Tian and Lidard, 2010), necessitating a full evaluation of

their skill before they can be recommended for operational use. In this study, precipitation from the ground gauge and 4 satellite products are used as main input in the hydrological model for streamflow simulation at Koshi river basin. This simulation result is compared with the observed streamflow which is more reliable than only to compare the satellite data with limited ground gauged data.

The various research was done on the comparison of satellite-based products with ground-based precipitation in term of statistical analysis at Koshi basin. Only the sole study was done by using ground-based precipitation on a rainfall-runoff model to evaluate the hydrodynamics. No satellite-based precipitation products are evaluated in the well performed hydrological model in that study area. So study focus on the evaluation of precipitation product on the well performed hydrological model in the study area.

1.3 Research question

The study is focused on open sources of satellite precipitation estimate product. Different satellite precipitation estimate products will be selected according to the relevance of the study area. The main research questions are

- i. Are satellite-based precipitation estimations good enough for hydrological modelling in absence of ground precipitation data?
- ii. Which are the best satellite-based precipitation products based on statistical performance?
- iii. Which products are suitable for flood modelling and water balance estimation?

1.4 Objective of study

The main objective of the study is to evaluate the performance of ground data and satellite-based precipitation products on the rainfall-runoff model.

1.5 Scope and limitations

The study will focus on ground-based data and open sources of satellite-based precipitation data on daily basis. Four numbers of satellite-based precipitation products and one hydrological model will be chosen according to the relevance of the study area based on literature review. In this case, Koshi river basin that lies in Nepal and Tibet part will be studied. The virtual stations will be used to estimate precipitation in the Tibet part of the study area. The limitations of the study are as follows:

- i. Missing data and data gap in the daily hydrological and meteorological data.
- ii. A limited number of gauge station at Himalayan part of basin and Aphrodite data set used in Tibetan part.

- iii. Land cover of Globcover of 2009 was taken which can't represent the past and future land use change.
- iv. Change in glacier area as per change in temperature is not applied in the model.
- v. The climate data (such as temperature, wind, sunshine hour, relative humidity) are extrapolated from 4 stations for the entire catchment.
- vi. Limited data and information on geology.
- vii. Soil depth is considered as 80 cm average for the entire basin.
- viii. No hydro- meteorological ground dataset for Tibetan part.
- ix. The stream width is taken as 10 m in the reach parameter file.
- x. Spatial distribution of precipitation such as according to a wide range of spatial scales, from small - scale ridge - valley gradients and orographic factor.

1.6 Organization of the thesis

This thesis constitutes altogether six chapters which are tabulated and illustrated in systematic order.

Chapter I: It consists of the brief introduction, statement of the problem, needs for study, research gap, scope and limitation of the study.

Chapter II: It describes the general feature of study area regarding physical feature, physiographic division, climate, soil, land use type and geology.

Chapter III: It deals with the literature review regarding satellite precipitation product, different verification methods, how hydrological model can be used to evaluate the precipitation products. Furthermore, it describes selection of J2000 hydrological model and limitation of hydrological model application in mountain and the Himalayan region.

Chapter IV: This chapter is completely based on the data source and methodology. It also elaborates the J2000 hydrological model in details considering different components and function. It provides detail information on the preparation of data set for the study area, how it processes in the hydrological model. The different preparation of input hydro- meteorological file, parameter file such as soil, land use, geology, Hydrological response units (HRUs), reach parameter, data processing by different tools such as GIS, QGIS with HRU delineation, Hydrus1D, R and Python script, HWSO viewer will be simultaneously discussed.

Chapter VI: It presents the result and discussion. It further elaborates statistical analysis of output, comparison of result with the graph, chart and final ranking of precipitation products.

Chapter VII: The last chapter describes the conclusions and discussions. The conclusions of the study are generated and future recommendations are drafted for the upcoming study. This chapter is followed by bibliography and annex.

CHAPTER II

2 Description of study area

2.1 General

Koshi is the largest river of Nepal also known as Saptakoshi for its seven tributaries namely Sun Koshi, Bhothe Koshi, Tama Koshi, Dudh Koshi, Barun, Arun and Tamur is a transboundary river between China, Nepal and India is one of the largest tributaries of the Ganges. The seven tributaries all join the main course of the river above Tribeni and emerge through the gorge at Chatara into the plains. Koshi river is the third biggest Himalayan river after Indus and Brahmaputra. The total length of the Koshi river is 720 km. The river basin is surrounded by the ridges separating it from the Yarlung Zangbo river in the north, the Gandaki in the west, the Mahananda in the east, and by the Ganges in the south (Wikipedia, 2017).

Figure 1: Location of Koshi basin and study area

The basin lies within latitudes 26 ° 51' and 29° 79'N, and longitudes 85° 24' and 88° 57' E. About 49×10^9 m³ of water flows contribute to Ganges river annually and end into the Indian ocean (Gleick, 2003). The majority of the population (almost 70%) in the basin depend on rain-fed and traditional agriculture for its livelihood (Dixit *et al.*, 2009). The hills and the Terai plains contribute the maximum area to agriculture in the basin. Water stress during the dry season and frequent floods during the monsoons are the biggest challenges in the Koshi basin (NCVST, 2009).

2.2 Physical features

2.2.1 General

The river enters the plain at Chatara through the historical and sacred temple at Barahachhetra in Nepal which is 5 km upstream of Koshi Barrage. Koshi river is the main tributaries that flow into Ganges river. The Koshi river passes through the 15 km narrow valley and reaches Chatara in Terai region (Dixit *et al.*, 2009). The river is transboundary in nature which originates from the Tibetan plateau, flows through the Himalayas and reach as at plain and enter India near Bhimnagar and travel 320 Km through the plains of north Bihar before finally joins the Ganga river near Kursela (Bapalu and Sinha, 2006). The river is controlled by artificial barrage at Hanuman Nagar downstream of Chatara with the purpose of hydroelectric generation and flood control under bilateral co-operation between Nepal and Indian government. The total length of Koshi river is 720 km and drains about 71,500 sq.km total area in Tibet, Nepal and India (Dixit *et al.*, 2009). The total area of basin upstream of Chatara station is about 57,722 sq.km in which 46% of the basin lies in Nepal. The seasonal flow in Koshi is highly fluctuating and annual flow at Chatara is 1,620 m³/s and the average discharge of the river is measured in Chatara gauging station ranges from 337 m³/s in dry months to 4,590 m³/s in wet months (Bista, 2014). The river is highly vulnerable to changes in the course and in last 220 year, the river had oscillated over 115 km (Dixit *et al.*, 2009). This river carries high amount of silt and sediment because of intense rainfall at monsoon season, steep gradient and tectonic instability (Lasiwa, 2016) and in one year, it carries about 120 million m³ of sediment to the Ganges (Dixit *et al.*, 2009). A devastating flood occurs at August 18, 2008, occurred in Koshi due to the breach of a spur at 12.6 km upstream of Koshi barrage only at the moderate flow of 4,770 m³/s (Lasiwa, 2016).

2.2.2 Major rivers in the study area

The river Koshi, also commonly known as Sapta Koshi, comprises of seven rivers namely (from west to east); Indrawati, Sunkoshi, Tamakoshi, Likhu, Dudhkoshi, Arun and Tamur as shown in Figure 2. Out of these rivers, three major rivers or tributaries originate in Tibet (JICA, 1985). They are Sunkoshi, Tamakoshi and Arun. The annual runoff of the tributaries of the Koshi river at Tribeni is as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Annual runoff of the tributaries of the Koshi river at Tribeni

S.N	River	Annual runoff (10 ⁶ m ³)
1	Sapta Koshi	50,900 (100%)
2	Sun Koshi	22,400 (44%)
3	Arun	18,300 (36%)
4	Tamur	10,100 (20 %)

(Source: JICA, 1985)

Figure 2: Major rivers in study area

2.3 Physiographic division

The basin experience huge elevation difference from 8848 m (Mountain Everest) to 60 m in the alluvial plains (Chen *et al.*, 2013). The basin is classified into four physiographical regions based on the elevation

and geography. The region comprises of six geological and climatic belts: the Tibetan plateau, the high Himalaya, the midland hills, the Mahabharat Lekh, the Chure (Siwalik range) and the Terai (Dixit *et al.*, 2009). Eight peaks over 8,000m including highest peak of the world; Mount Everest, 36 glaciers and 296 glacial lakes lie in the high Himalayas of the Koshi river basin (Wikipedia, 2017). The research study is mainly focused on the Nepalese and Tibetan part of the Koshi basin, upstream of Chatara. The Koshi river drains in the foreland of the Gangetic plain in India after flowing from Nepal. This study does not include the Indian part of the Koshi river basin. The Figure 4 shows the generalized cross section of the Himalayan region and its physiographic divisions.

Figure 3: Physiographic divisions of Koshi Basin

As per study conducted by Chen *et al.* (2013) the southern part of Koshi basin consists of broadly developed schist and slate rocks and quaternary deposits with a wide range of molasse, Siwalik gravels that are deposited in the south of lower Himalayas which are vulnerable to erosion from thin debris flow, flash flood and landslides in the arid area. The northern part of the middle Himalayan region in which igneous and metamorphic rocks such as granite gneiss, granite amphibolite gneiss, migmatite, etc are mostly found. The High Himalayas is characterized by mainly hard rocks such as granite and granite gneiss and Tibetan plateau is dominated by sedimentary rocks and the little portion of metamorphic rocks. The structural framework of Himalayan is influenced by three thrust via. Main Central Thrust (MCT), the Main Boundary Thrust (MBT) and the Main Frontal Thrust (MFT) which are spread over the Himalayan range (Upreti, 1999). These thrusts differentiate the tectonic zone in Nepal Himalayan

region which comprise of the higher Himalaya zone, lesser Himalaya zone, Siwalik zone and Terai region (Dahal and Hasegawa, 2008). These thrusts are assumed to be combined together in a low angle decollement known as the Main Himalayan Thrust (MHT) located at north deep below Himalaya.

Figure 4: Generalized cross section of the Himalayan region (Nepal, 2012 and Regmee, 2004)

2.4 Climate

The climate is arctic on the high Himalaya, which decreases with decreasing elevation from the alpine condition, cold temperate, warm temperate and tropical climate in the low lands of Terai (ICIMOD 2009). Spatial distribution of precipitation is also not uniform mainly due to the leeward and windward effects of the mountain. So the amount of precipitation differs with elevation and geology of the area. Precipitation patterns in the Koshi basin are directly associated with the South Asian monsoon. Maximum precipitation occurs at upstream and lowers windward slopes of the west and south-facing mountain barriers.

As per the study conducted by ICIMOD (2009), the study area has a difference in annual average temperature ranging from about 5° to 25°C. The daily temperature during the rainy season is comparatively low. The temperature is minimal in the month of January. The temperature during the dry season rises during the sunshine hours and decrease quite suddenly with the nightfall, and daily fluctuation in temperature is about 15° to 20°C. Humidity during the rainy season has a monthly average of about 90 % with the little daily variation in the humidity. Humidity in the dry season, on the other hand, varies widely and is about 18 %.

Mainly four seasons are prevalent in the region. They are winter (December - February), pre-monsoon period (March-May), monsoon period (June - September) and post-monsoon period (October -

November). About 80% of the total annual precipitation occurs during the month of June through September (Ueno *et al.*, 2008). During this period, the region receives intense rainfall which brings floods and widespread damage to property and lives. Temperature starts to rise after February and reaches its maximum level during the monsoon season. The rainy season coincides with the summer monsoon. The summer monsoon dominates the climate from May to September and westerly circulation dominates from November to March (winter monsoon).

2.5 Soil type

The huge variation of soils are found in the Himalaya region in terms of texture, mineral, content, depth and other physical characteristics and soil depth in higher Himalayan and are relatively thin due to the presence of rocky landscape and steep slope (Nepal, 2012). The lower part of the basin is dominated by a soil mixture of Acrisols, Cambisols, Lithosols, Gleysols, Histosol and which mostly contain sandy clay composed of organic matter with temporary wetness near the surface (FAO/IIASA/ISRIC/ISSCAS/JRC, 2012). These soil are more suitable for agricultural purpose. The higher Himalayas contain more glacier and permanent snow so it has negligible infiltration rate (Lasiwa, 2016).

Figure 5: Soil type at Koshi basin (adapted from FAO/IIASA/ISRIC/ISSCAS/JRC, 2012)

The soils in this area are mostly shallow and loose soil with sandy gravel and cobbles in valleys. Elevation higher than 5500 m mostly contains rocks and middle mountain regions soil in dark brown

colour and silt loam texture are in abundant amount (Sharma *et al.*, 2000).The soil map given below is prepared with data from Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD) Version 1.2. The Tibetan part of basin is dominated by Gelic Leptosols, hills and mountain is dominated by Dystric Cambisols and higher Himalayas part is dominated by Lithosol. Table 2 show the amount of soil distribution in the Koshi basin.

Table 2: Soil distribution in Koshi basin

Grid code	SoilID	Soil_Namd	Area (sq.km)	Percentage
1	Ah	Humic Acrisol	481.71	0.91
3	Bd	Dystric Cambisols	15425.60	29.01
7	I	Lithosol	7796.85	14.66
8	Je	Eutric Fluvisols	28.08	0.05
12	LVh	Haplic Luvisols	356.94	0.67
14	FLc	Calcaric Fluvisols	35.19	0.07
15	ARc	Calcaric Arenosols	30.38	0.06
17	ARh	Haplic Arenosols	56.00	0.11
18	GLk	Calcic Gleysols	12.00	0.02
19	LP	LEPTOSOLS	487.53	0.92
20	RGe	Eutric Regosols	170.69	0.32
21	PHh	Haplic Phaeozems	114.38	0.22
22	PHc	Calcaric Phaeozems	925.06	1.74
23	PHg	Gleyic Phaeozems	598.81	1.13
26	LPi	Gelic Leptosols	17759.83	33.39
27	CMi	Gelic Cambisols	2059.65	3.87
28	GLi	Gelic Gleysols	17.94	0.03
29	LPm	Mollic Leptosols	281.06	0.53
30	LPe	Eutric Leptosols	4741.94	8.92
31	CMc	Calcaric Cambisols	1698.81	3.19
32	ATa	Aric Anthrosols	103.56	0.19

(Source: adapted from FAO/IIASA/ISRIC/ISSCAS/JRC, 2012).

2.6 Land use and land cover

The land cover is developed as per European Space Agency GlobCover portal. The dataset Globcover2009_V2.3_Global_.zip is used for land use classification. The upper Tibetan part is dominated by bare land and sparsely vegetated grassland which account for more than 50 % of land cover. The Nepal part of the basin is dominated by agricultural land with the presence of deciduous, coniferous and mixed forest. Normally in the lower elevation area, the Terai and Siwalik region predominantly covered by tropical evergreen and deciduous riverine forest with mixed vegetation such as grassland and shrubland (Nepal, 2012). Most parts of the region depend upon rain-fed agriculture and some part of Terai have a systematic irrigation system. Table 3 is the coverage of land cover type in a study area.

Table 3: Land cover in Koshi basin

SN	Grid code	Land cover	Area	Percentage
1	17	Bareland/Per.Snow	18233.2	31.78
2	15	Grassland	13138	22.90
3	11	Agriculture Land	8262.74	14.40
4	14	Deciduous Forest	6651.25	11.59
5	12	Mixed Forest	3970.27	6.92
6	13	Coniferous Forest	3115.22	5.43
7	16	Shrubland	2338.81	4.08
8	222	Glaciers	1078.84	1.88
9	18	Waterbodies	423.623	0.74
10	19	Rocky Mountains	157.897	0.28

Source: adapted from Bontemps et al. (2013)

Figure 6: Land use and land cover (adapted from Bontemps et al. (2013))

Chapter III

3 Literature review

3.1 Satellite based precipitation products (SPPs)

Presently there are numbers of satellite based precipitation product (SPP) products that have been developed as blending Passive Microwave (PMW) and Infra-red (IR) sensors. PMW signals (10–37 GHz) sense thermal emission of raindrops and higher frequencies (85 GHz and higher) senses the scattering of upwelling radiation from the earth to space due to ice particles in the rain layer and tops of convective systems (Joyce et al., 2004). IR sensor uses cloud top temperature data for the precipitation estimation and has less application in the mid-latitudes due to the toughness of delineating rain and no rain clouds. The main disadvantage is less accuracy due to overestimating precipitation because they are affected by the problem of rain/no rain clouds discrimination (Giannakos and Feidas, 2012). Following are the SPPs that are used in this study and selection of the products justification are done in section 3.4.

3.1.1 Climate Prediction Center Morphing Technique (CMORPH)

CMORPH is one of the products of National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's (NOAA) Climate Prediction Center (CPC). CMORPH (CPC MORPHing technique) generate global precipitation product at very high spatial and temporal resolution. This technique uses precipitation estimates that have been derived from low orbiter satellite microwave observations exclusively, and whose features are transported via spatial propagation information that is obtained entirely from geostationary satellite IR data (CMORPH, 2017). This technique is not a precipitation estimation algorithm but a means by which estimates from existing microwave rainfall algorithms are combined. Therefore, this method is extremely flexible such that any precipitation estimate from any microwave satellite source can be incorporated.

CMORPH produces global precipitation analysis at very high spatial (8 km) and temporal (30 min) resolution starting from December 2002 and is available 60° N to 60° S. Three datasets are available in the format of 3-hourly with 0.25 ° lat/long, daily with 0.25 ° lat/long and 30 minutes with 8 km spatial resolution (Habib *et al.*, 2012). The new version of (V 1.0) is available from Jan 1998 to till date. Only there is minor difference between the older version (V 0.x) and the new version. The version 1.0 include the raw, satellite only precipitation estimates as well as bias-corrected and gauge-satellite blended precipitation products; while the Version 0.x only has the satellite-only products. The new version can be downloaded from ftp server at: ftp://ftp.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/precip/CMORPH_V1.0/. A detail description of this product is described in Joyce *et al.* (2004).

3.1.2 Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM)

TRMM is a joint cooperation program between National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) of U.S. and National Space Development Agency (NASDA) of Japan. The satellite came into existence on Nov 27, 1997, with aim of measuring precipitation and energy exchange in tropic and subtropical regions of the world. It consists of TRMM Microwave Imager (TMI), precipitation radar (PR), Visible and Infrared Radiometer System (VIRS), Earth Observing System (EOS) instruments which can measure atmospheric water vapour, cloud water and rainfall intensity (TRMM, 2017). The (TRMM) Multi-satellite Precipitation Analysis (TMPA) provide the precipitation at the resolution of (0.25°* 0.25° and 3 hourly). TMPA is capable to detect the large daily events by surface observation-based histogram of precipitation and evaluate the twice routine processing for TRMM which produce real-time monitoring after 9 hours (3B42RT) and post time high-quality research data after 10 to 15 days after the end of each month (Huffman *et al.*, 2007). The 3B42 and 3B43 products have been available since 1998 and data cover the domain from 50° N to 50° S. The details of the algorithm can be obtained from https://disc2.gesdisc.eosdis.nasa.gov/data/TRMM_L3/TRMM_3B42_Daily.7/.

3.1.3 Asian Precipitation - Highly-Resolved Observational Data Integration towards Evaluation (Aphrodite)

Aphrodite project offer the cost-free high-resolution data set for Asia. The data are developed from a ground base rain gauge network observation of 5000 to 12,000 valid stations which is nearly 2.3 to 4.5 times the data available through the global telecommunication system network and are available from 1951 to 2007 in continental scale on daily basis for Asia which include Himalayas, south and Southeast Asia and mountainous areas in the Middle East (Aphrodite, 2017). The data can be downloaded at <http://dias-dss.tkl.iis.u-tokyo.ac.jp/dl/storages/filelist/dataset:262>.

3.1.4 Multi-Source Weighted-Ensemble Precipitation (MSWEP)

MSWEP is new product which is derived from gauge, satellite and reanalysis data and has 3-hourly and daily temporal resolution and 0.1°, 0.25° spatial resolution of global-gridded precipitation data set covering 1979–2016. The version V1 and V2 are available and V2 are still in the preparation. In this study, the version V1 is used with daily temporal and 0.25° spatial resolution. This data have the advantage of wide range of data source including atmospheric reanalysis model to produce best possible precipitation estimate at the global scale (Beck *et al.*, 2017).

3.2 Selection of satellite-based precipitation products

Rain gauges collect precipitation data at a particular point during a specified interval of time. In Nepal, the interval of measurement is one day from 03:00 (Co-ordinate Universal Time) UTC to 03:00 UTC (i.e. 08:45 am to 08:45 am local time). The rainfall data are collected from Department of hydrology and meteorology (DHM), the sole authority for the collection and dissemination of hydrological and meteorological data. Ideally, the time recording of gauging station should be same as recorded by precipitation product.

A study conducted by Andermann *et al.* (2011), on precipitation products such as Aphrodite, CPC-RFE, TRMM- 3B42, TRMM-2B31, and GSMaP are evaluated for five watersheds in Himalaya region. The Aphrodite and TRMM- 3B42 products as observed in the five small watersheds as shown in Table 4 deliver good temporal variability, both on an annual and monthly scale. Aphrodite product at the Jhikhu Khola catchment in the lower mountain with an elevation of 1400 m exhibits nearly same precipitation value on daily basis compare to ground gauge because of Aphrodite are available for more than 30 years is the couple with good temporal resolution.

Table 4: Watershed under study

SN	Name	Region/Country	Area (Sq.km)	Elevation (m)
1	Bhetagad	Uttaranchal/India	24	1000-2000
2	Hillkot	Pakistan	15	1500-2700
3	Xizhuang	Yunnan/China	34	1750-3100
4	Yarsha Khola	Nepal	53	1000-3000
5	Jhikhu Khola	Nepal	111	800-2200

Source: (Andermann *et al.*, 2011).

A research conducted by Tong *et al.* (2014) based on precipitation evaluation on Tibetan plateau using the hydrological model. The streamflow simulation was done on the Variable Infiltration Capacity (VIC) hydrologic model in Yellow (Upper Yellow) and Yangtze (Upper Yangtze) river basins over the Tibetan plateau of four satellite products (TRMM-3B42-V7, TRMM-3B42RT-V7, PERSIANN, and CMORPH) shows that TRMM-3B42-V7 and CMORPH datasets have relatively better performance than the others. The 3B42RT product overestimate the gauge precipitation and PERSIANN is unable to follow the spatial and temporal pattern of the gauge precipitation estimates. The 3B42RT and PERSIANN show little representative streamflow simulation whereas CMORPH has good potential for hydrological application in that region, in addition, it has some underestimation. The performance of TRMM-3B42 shows similar performance to China Meteorological Administration (CMA) data in both monthly and daily streamflow. A study conducted by Hussian *et al.* (2016) conclude that CMORPH performs well over plain, mountainous, and glacial regions of Pakistan. As per the study conducted by Beck *et al.* (2017) on the

evaluation of 23 precipitation products for the period of 2000 to 2016 using sub-daily or daily dataset by calibrating the conceptual model HBV against streamflow records for each of 9,053 small to medium-sized ($< 50,000 \text{ km}^2$) catchments worldwide and comparing performance efficiency. The result shows that MSWEP products perform best than other products. With reference to literature review, I choose the ground gauge data, Aphrodite, TRMM 3B-42, MSWEP and CMORPH product for the further evaluation in hydrologic model from time period of 1998 to 2014 for my study area because the studies were carried out in similar physiographical and climatic context and data available for these products are from 1998.

3.3 Verification of satellite based precipitation products

The mountainous and Himalayan area has limited numbers of rain gauge or no rain gauge. In mountainous areas with a limited or no rain gauge, Satellite based precipitation product can provide information on rainfall amount, intensity, occurrence and distribution. However, there might be the possibility of uncertainty and affect the accuracy of prediction during rainfall-runoff model for flow simulation (Bitew and Gebremichael, 2011). Verification can be done at three levels such as country, physiographic and basin level. All of these studies have been focused on understanding the accuracy and its strength and weakness. The verification of estimate has been conducted at various spatial and temporal resolutions depending upon the expected field of application.

There are various methods of satellite based precipitation product with the rain gauge measurement which include visual verification, continuous statistics (mean absolute error (MAE), root mean square (RMSE), coefficient of co-relation (r^2) and mean-bias), and categorical statistics probability of detection (POD) and false alarm rate (FAR) and were based on daily, decadal (10 daily accumulation), monthly, and seasonal accumulation rain gauge and satellite estimated data. Continuous statistics is applied to evaluate the performance of the satellite products in quantifying the amount of rainfall. On another hand, categorical statistics were adopted to access rain detection capabilities which are more significant if the product will be applied in modelling of floods (Bajracharya *et al.*, 2015). POD (hits) and FAR (misses) are significant to predict the hydrological consequence of source of error in precipitation product (Derin and Yilmaz, 2014).

Islam *et al.* (2010) study on Nepal, compared TRMM product with ground rain gauge data on daily based from the period of 1998 to 2008 and conclude that trend with TRMM and observed rainfalls are similar but actual rainfalls were underestimated most of days and overestimated in a few days. Duncan and Biggs (2012), evaluate the seasonal accuracy of TRMM-3B42 over Nepal and shows that it underperformed in extreme rainfall estimation and didn't detect rainy days well. Satellite products are very much well correlated with observed rainfall for all seasons but overestimated the rainfall amount mainly monsoon season. The detection of extreme precipitation events is inaccurate in terms of rainy days and intensity in monsoon season. So Duncan and Biggs (2012) don't recommend the precipitation estimate in agricultural planning and water resource management and recommend on the development of rainfall gauge network in high relief region.

Bajracharya *et al.* (2015) compared the five high-resolution satellite rainfall products (CPC RFMODIFIED NSE.0, RFMODIFIED NSE.0-Modified, CMORPH, GSMaP, and TRMM 3B42) at different spatial and temporal resolutions (daily, decadal, monthly, and seasonal) with observed rain gauge data from 2004 to 2006 to determine their ability to fill the data gap and suitability for use in hydrological and water resources management applications in Brahmaputra River basin. Grid to grid (G-G) and catchment to catchment (C-C) method developed by the International Precipitation Working Group (IPWG) in Brahmaputra Basin of Asia were employed and RFMODIFIED NSE.0-Modified, TRMM 3B42, and CMORPH performed best which all detected heavy, moderate, and low rainfall but still significantly underestimated magnitude of rainfall, particularly in orographically influenced areas. Overall RFMODIFIED Nash Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) performed the best result in term of high correlation coefficient with observed data and low mean absolute error, root mean square error, and multiple biases and is reasonably good at detecting the occurrence of rainfall which is followed by TRMM 3B42.

Krakauer *et al.* (2013) evaluate the satellite precipitation product (TRMM 3B-43) with ground station based gridded precipitation over Nepal on the monthly time scale. The TRMM precipitation product shows an overall NSE of 0.49 which is similar to the gridded station-based product Aphrodite and other precipitation product GSMaP, CMORPH, PERSIANN-CCS were less accurate which shows averagely underestimated precipitation compared to station observations. None of the products fully relate the mean precipitation as per elevation was seen in the station observations.

Shrestha (2011) compare the two higher resolution satellite precipitation products, RFE 2.0 and GSMaP with ground based rain data over Nepal from year 2003 to 2006. The products underestimate the precipitation amount on an annual basis at which RFE by 29% and GSMaP by 48 %. On another hand these products perform well in flatter terrain and inaccurate with elevation increment. The product GSMaP showed higher correlation. RFE 2.0 precipitation underestimate the magnitude of precipitation in Bagmati basin using the product for streamflow measurement (Shrestha *et al.*, 2008).

Tramblay *et al.* (2016) studied the five different satellite-based products (TRMM-3B42 v6 and v7, RFE 2.0, PERSIANN-CDR, CMORPH1.0 version 0.x) in the 1,785 sq.km Makhazine catchment Morocco. Precipitation is first compared with the ground observation and ten rain gauges and four different interpolation methods (inverse distance, nearest neighbor, ordinary kriging and residual kriging with altitude) were used to calculate the set of interpolated precipitation reference fields. The hydrological model is used for simulation based on different precipitation inputs. The conclusion was made that all the four interpolation methods except (i) neighbor approach give similar and valid precipitation estimates at the catchment scale, (ii) TRMM-3B42 v7 product is the closest to observed precipitation, (iii) TRMM-3B42 v7 perform poor in daily time steps in hydrological model but found to be adequate to reproduce monthly discharge in the catchment. This process provides the basis of water resource modelling of data scarce catchment with satellite-based rainfall data in this region.

3.4 Application of hydrological modelling for satellite based precipitation assessment

Table 5: A detailed literature review of satellite based precipitation products evaluation on the hydrological model in Nepal and Tibetan plateau.

Author	Product	Model	Basin/country	Major finding
Bajracharya <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Modified and unmodified RFE	GeoSFM	Bagmati/Nepal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Underestimation of simulated flows in unmodified RFE and modified RFE data nearly match the observed discharge in terms of timing and amount of stream flow.
Ghaju and Alfredsen (2012)	TRMM and GSMaP	LANDPINE	Trishuli/Nepal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Point to pixel comparison give negative bias error for both product. TRMM shows good simulation result calibration and validation period with scaling factor of 2.24 for precipitation which is higher than that for gauge precipitation.
Liu <i>et al.</i> (2017)	PERSIANN-CDR and GLDAs	HIMS	The Yangtze, Tibet/ China	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simulation of PERSIANN-CDR and GLADS precipitation are close to observation but the simulated streamflow using gauge-based precipitation is higher than observed discharge.
Liu <i>et al.</i> (2017)	PERSIANN-CDR and GLDAs	HIMS	Upper Yellow, Tibet/ China	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gauge-based precipitation, GLDAS, and PERSIANN-CDR precipitation have similar good performance in simulating streamflow. PERSIANN-CDR product performs best compare to other products.
Tong <i>et al.</i> (2014)	3B42, 3B42RT, CMORPH, and PERSIANN	VIC	Upper Yellow and Yangtze, Tibet/ China	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The 3B42 and CMORPH perform better than the 3B42RT and PERSIANN at both plateau and basin scales. CMORPH have good potential for hydrological application in the basin with some of the general underestimates. The 3B42 attributes the similar performance to CMA (China Meteorological Administration) data in both monthly and daily streamflow simulations.
Alazzy <i>et al.</i> (2017)	CMORPH-CRT, PERSIANN-CDR, 3B42RT, and 3B42	HEC-HMS	Ganzi, Tibet/China	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The product 3B42 shows the best performance for streamflow simulations and even outperforms simulation driven by gauge data during the validation period. PERSIANNCDR shows the worst overall performance.
Nepal (2012)	Gauge	J2000	Dush Koshi and Tamor/ Nepal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The model performs well with NSE value greater than 80% representing well hydrological dynamic.
Tamrakar and Alfredsen (2013)	TRMM	Thornthwaite water balance	Narayani, Karnali, Koshi, Sunkoshi and Bagmati/ Nepal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A good estimation of monthly discharge through basins with an average NSE value of 0.8.

A hydrological model simulates hydrologic processes in a more holistic approach compared to many other models which primarily focus on individual processes or multiple processes at relatively small-or field-scale without full incorporation of a watershed area (Oogathoo, 2006). Hydrological model is significant tools to understand the different watershed components and their respective feature in hydrology. The transformation of rainfall into runoff over a basin is considered to be very complex hydrological phenomenon in the field of water engineering, as this process is highly nonlinear, time-varying and spatially distributed. Table 5 shows the review of the satellite based precipitation products evaluation on hydrological modelling on Nepal and Tibetan plateau.

3.5 Application of J2000 hydrological modelling in study area

The rainfall-runoff relationship is mostly used mathematical model for water resource management planning, flood forecasting and warning schemes. The hydrologic model system J2000 offers a physical-based modelling of the water balance of big catchment areas. A large basin in the Himalayan and mountain region attribute heterogeneity in terms of topology, soil type, land use, geology, elevation and other factor leads to complexity in the availability of data (Nepal, 2012). So mountain topography exhibit the unique climatic conditions in different elevation zone as per change in temperature with elevation. The J2000 model offers the heterogeneity by considering different hydrological response units (HRUs) approach (Flügel, 1995) which is an advantage over lumped or semi-distributed models. In addition, the model has higher flexibility and adaptability to integrate various components within the model framework without alteration in other existing modules, so glacier model is also integrated into J2000 model. Such type of flexibility and integration may not be possible in another model due to limited access to the model code. The glacier module considers the factor such as radiation, slope, aspect and debris covered. Moreover, snow module computes different stage of snow accumulation, metamorphosis and snowmelt processes considering various components of energy balance such as such as snow density, snow depth, slope, aspect and sublimation.

Also model is chosen because Dudh Koshi and Tamor subbasin based on literature review performs well in model efficiency results indicating that the simulations were equally good for high and low flows and provides important insights into the hydrological dynamics of the river basin which is the part of Koshi basin (Nepal *et al*, 2014 and Nepal, 2012). Furthermore, the calculation of the real evaporation, in consideration with different land use classes, is integrated into the model. Since the model shall be suitable for the modelling of big catchment areas of more than 1,000 km², it is ensured that the modelling can be carried out by means of the available base data on the national scale.

3.6 Challenges of hydrological modelling in the Himalayan region and Tibetan plateau

The accurate estimation of the spatial distribution of precipitation in the Himalayan region is the tough task for water resource study and understanding of high altitude hydrology due to lack of high altitude observation data. The limitation of data hinders the application of standard approaches that are based on data-driven models. Data scarcity increases the difficulty by preventing the application of system calibration procedure that identifies the parameter set which ensures the internal consistency in the simulation of the single hydrological component. Hydrological modelling is challenging in the Hindu Kush Himalayan mountain because of lack of hydro-meteorological and cryosphere data because internal inconsistencies might play the role in underestimation of precipitation input that can be compensated for by an overestimation of meltwater or might be hidden due to the complexity of feedback mechanisms that govern melt and runoff generation in such basins (Pellicciotti *et al.*, 2012).

The study conducted by Immerzeel *et al.* (2012) at Hunza basin in Pakistan which contains very large glacier system. The glacier melt cannot persist unless snow input is much higher than that observed in meteorological stations located in mountain valleys. So studies show there are strong positive vertical precipitation lapse rates.

The challenge of a model that used to study the hydrological dynamic of a Himalayan area might have following reason:

- i. Limitation of data that can feature the hydrological and meteorological parameter in a temporal and spatial basin (Sharma *et al.*, 2000) due to a low-density station network and a particular location (low altitude and valleys).
- ii. Unreliability due to lack of long-term records and if available the quality is in question due to remoteness and accessibility (Kattelmann, 1987) which results in inaccuracy during decisions concerning water resources management (Alford, 1992).

The model should compute and represent the important hydrological process of the Himalayan river which consists of high floods (monsoon season) and low flow (dry period) and some part of it is contributed by glacier and snow melt (Nepal, 2012). So, the hydrological model should able combat with such kind of limitation as utmost in meso- and macro-scale catchment where the heterogeneity of the catchment parameters increases with a decrease in data accuracy (Krause, 2002 and Alford, 1992).

Chapter IV

4 Data source and methodology

4.1 Methodology

A thorough literature review was carried out in order to gain knowledge about a rainfall-runoff model and satellite precipitation estimation and its products. Furthermore, a detailed study on previous studies about different satellite precipitation products and their application in hydrological modelling in Nepal and Tibetan region provide, reference for selecting the best estimate products and model for the study area. Analysis of hydrological and physical characteristics of the Koshi basin was done in order to gain a comprehensive understanding of the study area. The different data sets for Koshi basin are collected from different source or developed using the different tools such as Arc GIS, QGIS, Hydrus1D.4xx tools, Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD) viewer, R and Python script. The input file and parameter file are processed in the J2000 hydrological model to evaluate the performance of ground-based data and precipitation products. The results are compared by means of statistical analysis, charts and graph. The detailed methodologies are described below.

4.2 Derivation of time series climate data

The 43 stations ground-based data, climate stations (relative humidity, temperature, wind and sunshine duration, discharge) for the Nepal part of Koshi basin are collected from the Department of Hydrology and Meteorology (DHM), Government of Nepal. Figure 7 shows the rainfall, discharge and climate stations nearby boundary and within boundary of study area. The near boundary and within boundary rainfall stations are chosen based on the completeness and quality of data. Since RBIS used different interpolation method to fill the data gap in the climate station and nearby stations play a vital role to fill such data gaps. In J2000 model regionalization is based on Inverse distance weighing (IDW) for all climate station data except temperature data. Temperature lapse rate is introduced into the model because of limited data available which isn't suitable for the IDW method. The main demerits of IDW approach in lower distribution of temperature station is in the condition when less temperature difference between stations at higher and lower altitudes in some days, the regionalization approach calculate the higher temperature in higher altitude which is not true practically (Nepal, 2012). There is not the availability of ground-based data for Tibetan part, So 25 virtual stations are selected based on uniform distribution of rainfall station within a basin. The elevation of Tibetan part of the basin is determined by the corresponding average elevation of HRUs. The daily time series data for the virtual station is obtained from Aphrodite because the data is derived from distance weighted interpolated data set, from ground-based gauge station and interpolation is based on the station between 5,000 to 12,000, depending upon the availability of station, including consideration of orographic factor (Andermann *et al.*, 2011). The ground data from DHM at Nepal part of Koshi and Aphrodite at Tibetan part are primarily used as main input for calibration of J2000 modelling.

The Aphrodite data are available from the period of the year 1951 to 2007 in *.nc format. For this study, only the period from 1998 to 2007 is taken into consideration. Similarly, the TRMM 3B-42 is also available from period 1998 to 2016 in (*.nc) format. The time period for TRMM product is taken from 1998 to 2014. The R-Script is used to process remote sensing data (*.nc) file into raster tiff file (Villanuevar, personal communication, 2017). In this study the new version (V1.x) taken into consideration. The CMORPH raw product is downloaded and rasterize into the tiff format by the python script (Roherig, personal communication, 2017). The raster file from the period 1998 to 2014 based on 43 ground stations and 25 virtual stations are extracted into daily point value by R-script (Villanuevar, personal communication, 2017).

Figure 7: Location of rainfall, climate and discharge station at Koshi basin

Figure 8 shows the average monthly discharge and monthly cumulative precipitation in a study area. When the precipitation fall on the basin, the part of the water is lost as evapotranspiration, interception and part of the water is stored through percolation and infiltration in groundwater zone. In this study, the discharge is divided into the dry and wet flow. The dry period occurs in November to May and wet period occurs in June to October which is characterized by high rainfall and discharge. As we compare

between the precipitation and discharge, dry period discharge is greater than precipitation occurs at that time which elaborate water is released into a river as ice, snowmelt and base flow. The recharge of groundwater takes place during the wet period and subsequent release during a dry period.

Figure 8: Average monthly discharge and monthly cumulative precipitation in Koshi basin (DHM, 2017)

4.3 Hydro-meteorological data collection and management

Reliable and accurate hydrological and meteorological data have a wide range of application in the different sector such as mitigation of natural disaster, agriculture, aviation, public, mountaineering and climate and weather forecast. In Nepal, DHM is a sole organization which collect the data and maintain the accuracy. I got the opportunity to take the interview with the official of DHM, Ms Manju Basi and data collector, Mr Rudra Gurung. As per them, the accuracy is maintained by the pattern of data, if some unexpected increase and decrease of data are observed, those data are avoided in the final entry of the system. The effective data storage and effective handling are the basic requirement for meteorological and hydro-climatological research and need the strategies for data collection, transfer, storing and processing that ensure the good quality and consistency of the data. In this study, to manage and store the data, a River Basin Information System (RBIS) has been developed by means of the Adaptive Integrated Data Information System (AIDIS) at Institute for Technology and Resources Management in the Tropics and Subtropics (ITT), Technische Hochschule (TH), Köln. The TH, Köln RBIS can be accessed through link <http://rbis.itt.fh-koeln.de/> . RIBS has the ability to manage different types of environmental data with or without spatial characteristics with numerous set of metadata. It is efficient tools for the visualization, linking, analysis and processing of different types of data to support research, decision making, result dissemination and information discovery for all kinds of users (Zander and Kralisch, 2016). Furthermore, the data can be analyzed by the possibility of exploring and correlating

the same parameter and temporal resolution, distance, elevation etc and data gap could be filled by rule-based gap filling toolbox is provided within RBIS (OBIS, 2016). It is very much suitable for managing time-series data and provides various functions for analyzing data and filling data gaps, which is a vital pre-processing step for environmental data analysis (Kralisch *et al.*, 2009).

Figure 9: Observation of meteorological station at Nagarkot, Nepal.

Figure 10: Ganges River Basin Information System (RBIS)

4.3.1 Gange River Basin Information System (RBIS)

A prototype of RBIS named as Gange RBIS in which Koshi basin is part of Ganges basin, is developed for data storage, analysis and processing. The time series data from the period of 1998 to 2015 on the daily basis data for 43 station precipitation, 4 each daily (temperature, wind speed, sunshine hour, relative humidity) and one discharge station data are entered into RBIS. The Ganges RIBS can be accessed through link <http://rbis.itt.fh-koeln.de/GangesRBIS/metadata/start.php> . The missing data in time series are filled by a different method of interpolation such as Inverse distance weight (IDW) and elevation, regression, linear interpolation, neighbouring station and extrapolation. After filling the missing data, the data can be downloaded in different temporal resolution and statistics such as daily, monthly, annual, as a sum or average together with maximum and minimum values.

4.4 Missing hydro-meteorological data

The hydro-metrological ground-based data that obtained from DHM, Nepal period from 1998 to 2015 is analyzed. The data of each station is converted into the text format and upload in the Ganges RBIS. In the RBIS platform, there is a mechanism to show the data gap in stations. The cumulative data gap of each rainfall stations is given in Annex 2. As per the analysis, the stations Chainpur, Dharanbazar, Biratnagar Airport have complete time series data and the station Lahan has the highest data gap of 1,412 days. In the RBIS platform, the missing rainfall value is filled by interpolation with IDW with elevation. For this purpose, the 10 maximum and 5 minimum rainfall station value, an elevation which is close to particular station and coefficient of determination (r^2) value of 0.7 are taken as reference for interpolation.

The cumulative data gaps in relative humidity (RH), wind, sunshine, minimum temperature (Min. Temp) and maximum temperature (Max. Temp) station are shown in Table 6. The Biratnagar station shows the zero data gap in relative humidity and Max. Temp records while its show the highest data gaps in sunshine and wind records. Taplejung station has the lower data gaps in RH, Min. Temp and Max. Temp. The missing value for wind station is filled by IDW with elevation, IDW and linear interpolation, RH by nearest neighbourhood, sunshine by linear interpolation, temperature by linear interpolation, regression, IDW and IDW with elevation. The reference value set for the different interpolation are given below in Table 7 and 8. The interpolation method is selected based on trial and error method and how well the interpolate curve follow the previous and following curve pattern.

Table 6: Cumulative data gap of RH, wind, sunshine, Min. Temp and Max. Temp station

SN	Index	Station	Data Gap (Day)				
			RH	Wind	Sunshine	Min.Temp	Max.Temp
1	1206	Okhaldhunga	193	557	928	162	162
2	1307	Dhankuta	123	143	964	107	458
3	1319	Biratnagar Airport	0	577	1336	211	0
4	1405	Taplejung	104	365	1054	41	32

Table 7: Reference parameter for rainfall interpolation

SN	Interpolation method	Max. Station	Min. Station	r ²	Max distance(km)	Exponent
1	IDW with Elevation	10	5	0.7		2
2	IDW	10				2
3	Linear Interpolation	10	5	0.7	100	2
4	Linear Regression	10	5	0.7	100	2
5	Nearest Neighborhood	3	1	0.7	100	2

(Note: Exponent 2 represent the interpolation curve follow second-degree equation, Max. denote maximum and Min. denote minimum)

Table 8: Reference parameter for RH, wind, sunshine, Min. Temp and Max. Temp interpolation

SN	Interpolation method	Max. Station	Min Station	r ²	Max distance(km)	Exponent
1	IDW with Elevation	3	1	0.7		2
2	IDW	3				2
3	Linear Interpolation	3	1	0.7	100	2
4	Linear Regression	3	2	0.7	100	2
5	Nearest Neighborhood	3	1	0.7	100	2

(Note: Exponent 2 represent the interpolation curve follow second-degree equation, Max. denote maximum and Min. denote minimum).

4.5 Point to pixel rainfall comparison

Three precipitation stations are chosen based on the availability of lowest rainfall gap from the period 1998 to 2014 and the geophysical division. The Salleri station lies in the Himalayan region with rainfall gap of 121 days, Chainpur station lies on the hilly region with no rainfall gap and Chatara station lies in Terai region, is the point of discharge measurement. The point to pixel comparison is done with the daily scatter plot and standard verification analysis such as mean error (ME), absolute mean error (MAE), roots means square error (RMSE), coefficient of determination (r²) on daily, monthly and yearly basis. The scatter plot is also known as eye bell verification in which data is a plot in the same unit. In this approach, the gauge precipitation is plotted in x-axis against precipitation products in the y-axis. If the plotted lies around the 45° diagonal line, then data is co-related without any bias. The statistical performance is calculated by following formulae.

- i. Mean Error (ME): It is average difference between predicted and observed precipitation.

$$\text{ME is calculated by} = \frac{\sum(P_i - O_i)}{N} \quad (4.5.1)$$

Where, O and P, are observed and predicted value

ii. Mean Absolute Error (MAE): It measures the average magnitude of the error. It is calculated by $MAE = \frac{\sum |Pi - Oi|}{N}$ (4.5.2)

iii. Coefficient of determination (r^2) – According to Bravais- Pearson, (r^2) is calculated a

$$r^2 = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Oi - \bar{O})(Pi - \bar{P})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (Pi - \bar{P})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (Oi - \bar{O})^2}} \right)^2 \quad (4.5.3)$$

Where \bar{O} and \bar{P} are observed and predicted average value.

It measured the combined dispersion against the single dispersion of observed and predicted values. The (r^2) value range from 0 to 1 where 0 indicated that no correlation and 1 value indicate dispersion of the prediction is equal to that of the observation.

iv. Root Mean Square, $RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Oi - Pi)^2}$ (4.5.4)

The lower value indicates that data follows the good pattern compare to the observed value. The value of RMSE range from 0 to infinity. The zero value indicates the perfect match with observed data but one drawback is that it doesn't measure the under or overestimation.

4.6 J2000 modelling in Koshi basin

The J2000 modelling is distributed, a process oriented hydrological model used to compute the hydrological process simulation in meso- and macro-scale basin (Krause, 2001). It is operated in the Jena Adaptable Modelling System (JAMS) (Kralisch and Krause 2006 and Kralisch *et al.*, 2007), which is a software framework for component-based development and application of environmental models. The simulation of a hydrological process is carried out in an independent encapsulated model. It consists of different modules to represent the physio-hydrological process. Each module is characterized by a number of module parameters which should be adapted during the application. The model requires two types of main input at the initial process. The main input consists of the hydro-meteorological parameter such as precipitation, air temperature, humidity, wind speed, sunshine duration and physical parameters such as a topographic data in Digital Elevation Model (DEM), land use distribution, soil information and geological condition. The representation of a spatial distribution of topographic details, land use, soil and geology is converted into Hydrological Response Units (HRUs). HRUs have heterogeneously distributed entities with common climate, land use, and underlying pedo-topo-geological combination controlling their hydrological dynamics (Flügel, 1995).

The general layout of the J2000 model is listed below. It consists of glacier module which has been applied in Himalayan region (Nepal, 2012). The modelling system elaborates the four different runoff components as per their origin. The four different runoff components are following.

- i. Fast direct runoff (RD1): It consists of the runoff of sealed areas, of snow water, which drains within snow layers, and of surface runoff when saturation areas develop.
- ii. Slow direct runoff component (RD2): It is lateral hypodermic runoff within the soil zone, which reacts insignificantly slower than RD1.
- iii. Fast basis runoff component (RG1): It simulates the runoff from surface-near well permeable weathering zones which is the upper part of the ground water table or shallow aquifer.
- iv. Slow basis runoff component (RG2): It is runoff from joint aquifer or homogeneous loose rock aquifer which is part of deep aquifer.

Figure 11: Layout of J2000 hydrological model (Nepal et al., 2014 and Krause, 2001)

4.6.1 Hydrologic model components

The model consist of (i) **model parameter** files such as soil parameter file, land cover parameter file, hydro-geological parameter file, hrus and reach parameter files and (ii) **meteorological** input data such as absolute and relative humidity, measured flow passage at runoff, precipitation, sunshine duration, maximum and minimum temperature, wind velocity.

Following are the important modules in the J2000 hydrological model as per described by (Nepal, 2012).

i. Precipitation distribution module

The precipitation is categorized into rain and snow in J2000 modelling based upon the air temperature. Two calibration parameter base temperature (Trs) and threshold temperature ($Trans$) range (upper and lower boundary) are used. The precipitation below the threshold temperature ($Trans$) is considered as total snow precipitation and exceeding the base temperature (Trs) is considered as total precipitation in form of rain. The precipitation between these two ranges occurs the mixed precipitation. The actual amount of snow ($P(s)$) of daily precipitation subject to air temperature is calculated according to:

$$P_S = \frac{Trs+Trans-Temperature}{2.Trs} \quad (4.6.1)$$

The daily amount of snow (Ps) or amount of rain (Pr) is calculated according to

$$Ps = \text{Precipitation. } Ps \text{ (mm)} \quad (4.6.2)$$

$$Pr = \text{Precipitation. } (1-Ps) \text{ (mm)} \quad (4.6.3)$$

- ii. Interception module: Keeping the high value of parameters of snow and rain will store more water on leave surfaces which leads to higher evapotranspiration and less water available soil module. The maximum interception capacity ($Intmax$) is calculated according to the following formula.

$$Intmax = \alpha \cdot LAI \text{ (mm)} \quad (4.6.4)$$

α ... storage capacity per m^2 leaf area against the precipitation type [mm]

LAI ... LAI of the particular land-use class provided in land-use parameter file

- iii. Snow module: The module mainly describes the accumulation, melting and subsidence phases of a snowpack.
- iv. Glacier module: It takes into the account of snowmelt, ice melt and rain runoff which supply to nearby reach as overland flow (RD1).
- v. Soil module: The input for the soil module is snowmelt and precipitation in the form of rain. The middle pore storage (MPS) and large pore storage (LPS) represents the water holding capacity of the soil.

- vi. Groundwater module: The groundwater module receives input from unsaturated soil zones (soil water module) in a two storage compartment of a groundwater zone i.e. upper groundwater zone (RG1) and lower groundwater zone (RG2).
- vii. Routing: It consists of two routing components. The lateral routing serves to simulate lateral flow processes in the catchment area from one model entity (HRU) to the next until the water finally reaches to stream. The reach routing describes flow processes in a stream channel.

The regionalization approach of input data sets are described by Krause (2001) & (2010) and Nepal (2012) and explained in the link http://ilms.uni-jena.de/ilmswiki/index.php/Hydrological_Model_J2000.

4.6.2 Calculation of evapotranspiration

The evapotranspiration is calculated using the Penman-Monteith equation. The one parameter that should be defined is existing moisture content of a soil. The reducing effect of moisture content is adjusted by suitable reduction function. The day and night evaporation is taken into account in one value represented by day value (index d) and a night value (index n). The calculation for the day and night is carried out according to the following equations and value of one-day evaporation is a sum of these two values.

$$ETP_d = \frac{1}{L_d} \cdot \frac{S_d \cdot (R_{Nd} - G_d) + \rho \cdot c_p \cdot \frac{e_{sd} - e_d}{r_a}}{s_d + \gamma_d \cdot \left(1 + \frac{r_{sd}}{r_a}\right)} \cdot \left(\frac{S_0}{24}\right) \quad (4.6.5)$$

$$ETP_n = \frac{1}{L_n} \cdot \frac{S_n \cdot (R_{Nn} - G_n) + \rho \cdot c_p \cdot \frac{e_{sn} - e_n}{r_a}}{s_n + \gamma_n \cdot \left(1 + \frac{r_{sn}}{r_a}\right)} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{S_0}{24}\right) \quad (4.6.6)$$

With

$L_{d,n}$... latent heat of evaporation [Wm^{-2}] per [mmd^{-1}]

$s_{d,n}$... slope of the vapor pressure curve [$hPaK^{-1}$]

$R_{N d,n}$... net radiation [Wm^{-2}]

$G_{d,n}$... soil heat flux [Wm^{-2}]

ρ ... density of the air [kgm^{-3}]

c_p ... specific heat capacity of the air for constant pressure [$Jkg^{-1}K^{-1}$]

$e_{sd,n}$... saturation vapor pressure [hPa]

$e_{d,n}$... vapor pressure [hPa]

r_a ... aerodynamic resistance of the land cover [sm^{-1}]

$\gamma_{d,n}$... psychrometric constant [hPaK^{-1}]

$r_{sd,n}$... surface resistance of the land cover [sm^{-1}]

S_0 ... astronomic possible sunshine duration [h]

The detail computation is explain in http://ilms.uni-jena.de/ilmswiki/index.php/Hydrological_Model_J2000.

4.7 Preparation of data set for J2000 modelling

In this study, the Koshi basin that lies on the part of Nepal and China is taken into consideration. To evaluate the performance of precipitation product on J2000 modelling, the various dataset has to be prepared such as rain, relative humidity, sunshine hour, wind speed, temperature, runoff and soil parameter, land use, hydrogeological parameter, HRU and reach etc. The hydrological model was used as a tool to analyses precipitation products based on the runoff generation by respective products.

4.7.1 Hydro-meteorological data

The input file of the hydrological model consists of rain, relative humidity, sunshine hour, wind speed, temperature. The time series from 1998-01-01 to 2014-12-31 is taken for analysis. All the input file should be prepared in .dat format and parameter files in .par format. All the data should be prepared in the specific format and missing value is represented as -9999. The file other than precipitation is kept constant during the model run.

4.7.2 Model parameter file

It is developed and quantified in GIS environment and their value is static during modelling application (Kralisch and Krause 2006). The model parameters consist of land use, soil, geology, HRUs and reach parameter. These parameter files are developed with the soil, land cover, geology, Digital Elevation Model (DEM) in raster format with the certain resolution. During delineation of HRUs, this raster file should be converted into same resolution.

4.7.3 Soil parameter file

The soil parameter file is prepared with help from soil raster file and hydrus 1D software. The soil raster resolution of 896m is downloaded from the website of Harmonized soil database website at

<http://webarchive.iiasa.ac.at/Research/LUC/External-World-soil-database/HTML/> .The HWSD consist of 30 arc-second raster database with 16,000 different soil mapping unit that combines existing regional and national updates of soil information worldwide (SOTER, ESD, Soil Map of China, WISE) with the information contained within the 1:5,000,000 scale FAO-UNESCO soil map of the world (FAO/IIASA/ISRIC/ISSCAS/JRC, 2012). The soil raster file is clip approximately to Koshi basin size and projected to WGS_1984_UTM_Zone_45N. The raster file is converted into polygon in Arc GIS platform. The dominant soil in the basin is identified by the MU_Global code. The HWSD Microsoft access database of file HWSD_DATA is exported into excel file. The HWSD_DATA excel file is connected with shapefile as per common MU_GLOBAL. Two type of soil coding system is found in soil database, they are SU_SYM74 and SU_SYM90. The dominant soils are re-classify to code number 1 to 35. The basin consist of 21 distinct dominant soil class in which Tibetan part is dominated by Gelic Leptosols (33.4%) and Eutric Leptosols (8.9%) Gelic Cambisols (3.8%), Calcaric Cambisols (3.2), Calcaric Phaeozems(1.7%), Gleyic Phaeozems (1.1%), for higher Himalayan part is dominated by Lithosol (14.6%) and hill part is dominated by Dystric Cambisols (29%) and other distinct soils have less than 1%.

The HWSD data give the full information on the percentage of sand, silt and clay of top and subsoil and its corresponding USDA texture classification. The software component Rosetta inside 'HYDRUS 1D 4.xx' to understand the pedo-transfer functions of soils in three different hypothetical pressure methods (0 mbar, 60 mbar and 15,000 mbar). Hydrus-1D 4.xx software is used to calculate the air capacity (equivalent to large pore storage (LPS)) and usable field capacity (equivalent to middle pore storage (MPS)) by inputting the soil texture of top and subsoils and its corresponding USDA texture class value. The soil zone of each response unit is classified according to the specific pore volumes of the soil (Scheffer and Schachtschabel, 1984).

- i. The water stored in the shallow soil zone with the fine pore ($< 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ diameter) and soil moisture tension of 15,000 mbar represent the state of a permanent wilting point.
- ii. The middle pore storage (MPS) represents the pores with a diameter of 0.2 to 50 μm , (pressure equivalent between 60 to 15,000 mbar), corresponding to the usable field capacity.
- iii. The water stored in large pore storage (LPS) (coarse and macro pores) with a diameter of $>50 \mu\text{m}$ (pressure equivalent to less than 60 mbar) cannot hold water against gravity which is state of saturated soil condition.

The top and sub soil depth of each MU_Global is calculated with help of HWSD viewer. The value of soil parameters are listed in Annex 4.

4.7.4 Land use parameter

The land-use parameter is prepared from the land use and land cover of the basin which influences the hydrology of that region. The land use cover raster file of resolution 300m is download from http://due.esrin.esa.int/page_globcover.php of GlobCover 2009 (Global Land Cover Map). The map is

in geographic coordinates in a Plate-Carrée projection (WGS84 ellipsoid). Glob Cover is an ESA initiative which began in 2005 in partnership with JRC, EEA, FAO, UNEP, GOF-C-GOLD and IGBP. ESA makes available the land cover maps, which cover 2 periods: December 2004 - June 2006 and January - December 2009. The aim of the project was to develop a service capable of delivering global composites and land cover maps using as input observations from the 300m MERIS sensor on board the ENVISAT satellite mission. The land use raster file is clip approximately to Koshi basin size and projected to WGS_1984_UTM_Zone_45N. The raster file is converted into polygon into Arc GIS platform. The 17 thematic land use cover is found in a basin which is reclassified into 10 thematic land use based on the similar effects on hydrological dynamics. For instance, post-flooding or irrigated croplands and rain-fed croplands is reclassified as agriculture land. Furthermore, permanent snow and ice layer of the global cover are assumed as bare land because snow accumulation is computed within J2000 model. The land uses are reclassified by reviewing different literature are listed below.

The GlobCover data at higher altitude is found to be less reliable. So re-classification is done on subjective judgement based on expert knowledge, field knowledge and literature (MoFSC, 2002). The glacier layer is added into the GlobCover by mosaic the glacier raster with land cover raster in Arc GIS platform. The glacier layer is developed from satellites, the topographic map, and field-based observation (Nepal, 2012). The following parameter should be calculated to put input in J2000 modelling.

The data source for the albedo is taken from Giovanni platform at <https://giovanni.gsfc.nasa.gov/giovanni/>. Minimum surface resistance for water-saturated soil for 12-month data is taken from (Nepal, 2012) and Leaf area index, effective height, root depth is taken from different literature and SWAT 2009 database of crop use. The detail result of land use parameter is attached in Annex 5.

4.7.5 Geological parameter

The basin is classified into four physiographical regions based on the elevation and geography. The region comprises of Terai (60 m to 200 m), hill (200-4000m), Himalayan region (above 4000 m) and trans-mountain region lies north of the Himalaya and extends into the Tibet (Bharati *et al.*, 2014). Due to lack of detail information of geology in the area, based on the literature review the geology of study area is divided into the glacier, higher Himalaya, (mountain and Siwalik) and Trans- Himalayan (Tibetan part). As per (Uprety, 1999), gneisses schists and marbles dominate the higher Himalayan zone and Tethyan sediments (limestones, shale, sandstone etc.) belonging to the Tibetan- zone and schist, phyllite, gneiss, quartzite, granite, limestone geologically belonging to the lesser Himalayan and hilly zone. The geological parameter values are adapted from the (Nepal, 2012) and Schwarze (1999) for this study. It is assumed that there is no storage of water in upper and lower groundwater table in glacier zone. The geological parameter's value are mentioned in Annex 6.

Table 9: Reclassification of land use and land cover at study area

Value	Label	Re-Class	Land Type
11	Post-flooding or irrigated croplands (or aquatic)	11	Agriculture land
14	Rain-fed croplands	11	
20	Mosaic cropland (50-70%) / vegetation (grassland/ shrubland /forest) (20-50%)	11	
30	Mosaic vegetation (grassland/shrubland/forest) (50-70%) / cropland (20-50%)	12	Mixed Forest
110	Mosaic forest or shrubland (50-70%) / grassland (20-50%)	12	
40	Closed to open (>15%) broadleaved evergreen or semi-deciduous forest (>5m)	13	Coniferous Forest
100	Closed to open (>15%) mixed broadleaved and needle-leaved forest (>5m)	13	
50	Closed (>40%) broadleaved deciduous forest (>5m)	14	Deciduous Forest
70	Closed (>40%) needle-leaved evergreen forest (>5m)	14	
120	Mosaic grassland (50-70%) / forest or shrubland (20-50%)	15	Grassland
140	Closed to open (>15%) herbaceous vegetation (grassland, savannas or lichens/mosses)	15	
130	Closed to open (>15%) (broadleaved or needle-leaved, evergreen or deciduous) shrubland (<5m)	16	Shrubland
180	Closed to open (>15%) grassland or woody vegetation on regularly flooded or waterlogged soil	16	
200	Bare areas	17	Bareland/Per.Snow
220	Permanent snow and ice	17	
210	Water bodies	18	Waterbodies
150	Sparse (<15%) vegetation	19	Rocky mountains

Source: adapted from Bontemps et al. (2013)

4.8 Digital Elevation Model (DEM)

DEM is the specialized database that gives the information on the physiographic feature. It is used to quantify the characteristics land surface. The distributed model J2000 required the detail data on the basin characteristics such as basin size, boundary, slope, aspects, channel network and contributing sub-catchments (Nepal, 2012). For most regional or global applications, data from the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) can be used. In this study, DEM of 90m resolution SRTM_54_07 is obtained from NASA Shuttle Rader Topographical Mission (SRTM) at CGIAR-CSI Geo portal with a vertical error less than 16m. The DEM file is processed to fill data voids and has a wide range of application for sustainable development and resource conservation in the developing world. The DEM file in this study is used in the delineation of basin, sub-catchment and HRUs. The digital elevation

model of SRTM 90m digital elevation data resolution can be downloaded at <http://srtm.csi.cgiar.org/SELECTION/listImages.asp>.

4.9 Hydrologic Response Units (HRUs)

Leavesley *et al.* (1983) develop the concept that basin can be divided into sub-areas homogeneous in their hydrologic response, termed HRU. HRU is the smallest spatial unit of a model which have common topographic variables such as elevation, slope and aspect, and geographic variables, such as soil type, vegetation type and precipitation distribution. This idea provides the efficient way to describe the basin where simulation at field level are complex and computation not feasible (Kalcic *et al.*, 2015). Flügel, (1995) defined HRUs as spatial model entities which are distributed, heterogeneous structured entities having a common climate, land-use, soil, and geology controlling their hydrological dynamics and HRU hydrological process dynamic is relatively small compare to dynamic to other HRU. The region which contains similar characteristics of a slope, aspects, land-use, soil and geology and similarity in hydrological behaviour are merged to develop HRU.

4.9.1 Delineation of HRUs

HRU delineation can be done with help of QGIS with HRU feature and web-based delineation at a website: [http://jams.uni-jena.de/ilmswiki/index.php/WebHRU Tutorial](http://jams.uni-jena.de/ilmswiki/index.php/WebHRU_Tutorial). The main files need for delineation are digital elevation model (DEM), hydrological station, soil, land-use and hydro-geology. All the file should be in *.tiff format with the same resolution. In this study, the delineation was done manually with Q-GIS. The execution platform is isolated with help of preconfigured, virtual machine responsible for data preparation and the calculation of HRUs in Q-GIS. A plugin is developed for process chain.

Following are the step for delineation of HRUs.

- i. All the rasters (DEM), soil, land-use and hydro-geology should be projected into WGS_1984_UTM_ZONE_45N with clip area slightly greater than a watershed area in the arc- GIS platform.
- ii. All the projected raster file should be resampled into 250 m resolution and the setup is done by uploading all the file including gauge station into QGIS with HRU delineation feature.
- iii. The preparation phase consists of default filling of DEM file to delete the local sink.
- iv. Re-classification of slope and aspect is done.
- v. Water- flow process is computed to derive the water supply network, flow accumulation and flow direction and for partial catchment areas a threshold value (minimum size of basins) 1500 is defined.
- vi. The outlet of a watershed is defined to delineate the watershed area. A Chatara station is coincided with streamline and proceed.

- vii. During the overlaying the file, it creates small areas which are not suitable as HRU. So, it can be eliminated by defining the minimum size of an HRU cells. The value of 24 is defined in this study.
- viii. The topology module computes the N:1 topology (HRUs can drain in only one neighbouring HRU/river section), N: M topology (HRUs can drain in several neighbouring HRUs/river sections) and water topology (topological combination of all river sections).
- ix. At last, statistics are computed by converting HRU raster file into shapefile. The shapefile consist of information about elevation, area, aspect, coordinates (x,y), land-use type (landuseID), hydrogeology (hgeoID) and soil (soilID). The HRUs are interconnected for lateral routing to simulate lateral water convey from HRU to an HRU and were further connected to a nearby reach for reach routing. The column (to_poly) defines the HRU which passes water to the next HRU.

The delineation of HRUs processes provides HRU and reach parameter files in the notepad format. The sample result of HRU delineation is given in Table 10. If the HRU drain to another HRU, then the type will be 2. If HRU drains in channel part, then the type is 3. However, the lateral routing connection between HRUs should be checked if HRUs representing glaciers ID. All the HRUs should be checked manually to ensure the connection of glacier-HRU to another glacier-HRU or drain in streamlines. Because, if any HRU from a non-glacier-HRU is connected to a glacier-HRU through lateral routing, the water conveyed by the non-glacier HRUs (into Interflows (RD2 and RG1) and base flow (RG2) will vanish in the glacier HRU (Nepal, 2012). The study area consists of 12,661 units of HRUs. The area of HRUs range from 62,500 m² to 135,812,500 m².

4.10 Reach parameter

The reach parameter file contains the information regarding the stream properties, network to compute reach routing. It defines the structure of flow topology by noting the ID for every reach into which it transfers. It is automatically generated during HRUs delineation. For eg, the Hru ID 2 drain directly to Hru ID 20 and Hru ID 12 contribute water to Hru ID 35 which finally flows to Reach ID 848. The reach file consists of the information that are shown in Table 11. The basin consists of 342 distinct reaches.

4.11 Optimization of model parameter

The J2000 model is the distributed which required 36 parameters for model simulation. The sensitivity test of 36 parameters is done. The sensitivity test is done by adjusting the different value of the parameter within in permissible range. The change of parameter by a small fraction that causes the change in simulation result significantly is known as a sensitive parameter. Gupta *et al.* (2005) suggested three methods of model calibration. They are a trial-and-error method, ii) automatic or numerical parameter optimization and iii) a combination of both methods. The trial and error method involves the manual parameter adjustment with a number of simulation run and recommended when graphical representation

are highly important. The automatic calibration is done by using numerical algorithm over a large number of iteration to optimize the parameter in a systematic way. The third method consists of the combination of these process. The main significant of this method is a possibility of defining clear model-parameter boundaries (Nepal, 2012).

In this study, a third method is employed. The optimization process is done in Jam Builder platform and JAMS Cloud Server Environment for Remote Simulation developed by Friedrich Schiller University, Jena. First of all, the configuration of efficiency is done choosing the monsoon season and peak discharge as the main factor. The configuration of the optimizer is done in the NSGA2 platform choosing most sensitive parameter on parameter configuration in left-hand side and efficiency to be normalized on an objective configuration on the right-hand side. The model is optimized in OPTAS platform and calculated the optimized parameter in a number of iteration. Again, the corresponding model parameter having a lower value of normalizing efficiency are checked as per hit and trial error method. The most suitable values for these parameters which give the best performance efficiency are chosen for the model calibration. The optimization process is repeated for each individual set of precipitation products. This process develops the each individual set of optimized parameter and applies in the two methods of calibration explain in section 4.12.

Table 10: Hydrological Response Units (HRUs) generation by Q-GIS

ID	x	y	elevation	area	type	to_poly	to_reach	slope	aspect	flowl	soilID	landuseID	hgeoID
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
999999	9999999	9999999	10000	9999999	3	999999	999999	90	360	999999	9999	9999	9999
n/a	m	m	m	m ²	n/a	n/a	n/a	deg	deg	m	n/a	n/a	n/a
1	441986	3221748	5552	5187500	2	20	0	14.445	268	0	26	15	4
2	440486	3219998	5477	3687500	2	20	0	13.889	264	0	26	15	4
3	432236	3220498	5327	3750000	2	5	0	19.02	269	0	26	15	4
4	443486	3218498	5473	6375000	2	21	0	15.105	263	0	26	15	4
5	435486	3220498	5228	6250000	2	24	0	11.744	268	0	26	15	4
6	436361	3217748	4979	5375000	2	33	0	9.508	264	0	26	15	4
7	437236	3219748	5332	7312500	2	13	0	9.845	261	0	26	15	4
8	439236	3220498	5377	4875000	2	7	0	10.353	214	0	26	15	4
9	430361	3218998	5433	4562500	2	11	0	15.14	141	0	26	15	4
10	370361	3216998	4988	4937500	2	19	0	7.947	253	0	26	15	4
11	432111	3218498	5308	3750000	2	3	0	15.994	197	0	26	15	4
12	368236	3218498	4895	3687500	2	35	0	5.957	265	0	26	17	4
13	438361	3215748	4933	4562500	2	55	0	7.825	260	0	26	12	4
14	440361	3216748	4963	7937500	2	44	0	7.491	273	0	26	15	4
15	365486	3217498	4991	5312500	2	35	0	10.824	318	0	26	17	4

(In Table 10, ID denotes the HRU number, to_poly represent drain HRU ID , flowl represent flow length, the second row represent the minimum limit value of the corresponding parameter, the third row represent maximum limit value of the corresponding parameter and fourth column represent unit of parameter, where n/a is not available, m is meter and deg is degree)

Table 11: Reach generated during Hydrological Response Units (HRUs) delineation

ID	length	to reach	slope	rough	width
0	0	0	0	0	0
999999	99999	999999	90999999	9999	99999999
n/a	m	n/a	%	n/a	m
498	8200	0	1.8415	30	10
500	3414	498	1	30	10
502	3371	500	3.8564	30	10
504	23339	500	1	30	10
506	3018	504	6.2956	30	10
508	26399	504	1.5227	30	10
510	2811	508	1	30	10
512	6286	510	2.4817	30	10
514	11425	510	1	30	10
516	36792	514	1.1441	30	10
518	28867	516	1.343	30	10
520	4725	518	1.5873	30	10
522	854	518	1.4684	30	10
524	11286	522	1.5228	30	10
526	16132	524	7.7114	30	10

(Note: ID denote the reach number, the second row represent the minimum limit value of the corresponding parameter, the third row represent maximum limit value of the corresponding parameter and the fourth column represent unit of parameter, where n/a is not available, m is meter)

4.12 Model calibration and validation

The main objective research on a hydrological model is to improve the accuracy of model application. A parameters that are used in the hydrological model are the key factor that influences the accuracy of model simulations (Muleta and Nicklow, 2005). Past research and study revealed that intensive measurement of parameter value at field level don't have desired result (Kherde, 2015). Some of the model parameters are technically and economically not feasible practically for a huge area (Refsgaard, 1997). Model calibration is defined as a setting of a parameter within recommended ranges to improve the relationship between observed and simulated results which is done prior to application of hydrological model (Cooper *et al.*, 2007; Tolson and Shoemaker, 2007).

As per method explained in Klemes (1986) for calibration and validation, split sample test method is applied. In this method, the available time series data is split into two segments, one for calibration and other for validation. If the time series of data is too long, the data can be split into two half for calibration and validation and result from both adjustments are compared. If the data is not too long, the splitting should be done based on first 70% of the record for calibration and the last 30% for validation or the last 70% for calibration and the first 30% for validation. According to Refsgaard (1996), a model is validated in the method when its accuracy, predictive capacity in verification period are within permissible limits. The model parameter should be adopted only when the validation results are acceptable and similar. The calibration is done in two methods which are explained below.

i. Method I: calibration procedure using gauged precipitation datasets as main input.

In this study, the time series from 1998 to 2014 is considered but Aphrodite consists of data from 1998 to 2007. So, the model is calibrated based on the combination of ground gauge and Aphrodite product in which time series is split into 1998 to 2002 for calibration and 2003 to 2007 for validation. The parameter value used in the gauge calibration is again applied for calibration of the individual precipitation products.

ii. Method II: calibration procedure using individual satellite based precipitation as main input

In this method, the precipitation is calibrated directly by using individual satellite based precipitation. In this approach, the time series from 1998 to 2014 which is split into 1998 to 2006 for calibration and 2007 to 2014 for validation for individual satellite based precipitation products simultaneously.

4.13 Simulation result of the J2000 modelling

The J2000 modelling gives the various simulation output such as mean daily precipitation, rain, snow, runoff, interflow, groundwater recharge, potential and actual evapotranspiration, interception, snow melt, snow depth, percolation, saturated large and medium pore storage etc. In the result and discussion, we only discuss the simulation result of the precipitation and discharge because only observed precipitation and discharge data is available and other parameters don't have the observed data for large scale of Koshi basin. The simulation precipitation result is analyzed with standard verification such as mean error (ME), absolute mean error (MAE), RMSE, r^2 and NSE on daily, and graphical representation on monthly and yearly basis only in the method of Method I. The simulated discharge is analysis based on the graph and standard verification for the both method. The detail standard verification analysis is explained below with the computation formulae.

4.13.1 Standard verification of simulated discharge

The evaluation of hydrologic model behaviour and performance is done by simulated and observed variables most commonly used objective functions for hydrologic simulations (Krause *et al.*, 2005). The main objective to evaluate in the hydrological model is i). to estimate and predict the historic and future hydrological behaviour. ii). further improvement of a model in term of adjustment of model parameter, structure. The most basic method of evaluation of model is the subjective and objective estimate of simulated value to observed value. The subjective assessment is related to timing, rising limb, falling limb, and base flow whereas objective assessment includes error between the simulated and observed hydrologic variable.

As per (Krause *et al.*, 2005) following statistical performance was calculated during J2000 model simulation.

- i. r^2 (same as explain in equation number (4.5.3))
- ii. NSE: The regression coefficient or the measure of the model efficiency discussed by Nash and Sutcliffe (1970) is calculated as follows.

$$NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum(Oi - Pi)^2}{\sum(Oi - \bar{O})^2} \quad (4.13.1)$$

The measurement of NSE with higher value indicate that watershed has higher dynamic. The value range from $-\infty$ to 1 where 1 value is a perfect fit. NSE value less than 0 describes that observed time series is a better predictor than a model. The main limitation of this parameter is that larger values are overestimated and smaller value are neglected (Legates and McCabe, 1999). It doesn't respond well to systematic model because of underprediction during low flow season.

- iii. RMSE (same as explain in equation (4.5.3))

- iv. PBIAS (Relative percentage volume error) = $\frac{\sum(Pi - Oi)}{\sum Oi}$ (4.13.2)

- v. AVE (absolute volume error) = $\frac{\sum |(Pi - Oi)|}{\sum Oi}$ (4.13.3)

- vi. Modified forms of Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (Modified NSE): In this method, differences are not squared but their absolute values are applied. The modified form of Modified NSE is calculated as follows.

$$\text{Modified NSE} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |(Oi - Pi)|^j}{\sum_{i=1}^n |(Oi - \bar{O})|^j} \quad \text{with } j \in \mathbb{N} \quad (4.13.4)$$

If $j=1$, the overestimation of the flood peaks is reduced significantly, resulting in the overall evaluation. When the higher flows are significant for eg. Flood forecast j value can be increased to 2.

Where,

O_i= Observed discharge P_i= Predicted discharge

According to Giang and Phuong, 2010

$$\text{vii. Peak error} = \frac{(Q_{ip} - q_{ip})}{q_{ip}} \quad (4.13.5)$$

$$\text{viii. Wave Error} = \frac{1}{n} \sum \frac{(Q_i - q_i)}{Q_{ip}} \quad (4.13.6)$$

Where,

Q_i = Measured stream flow,

Q_{ip} = Measured peak

q_i = Simulated stream flow ,

q_{ip} = Simulated peak

n = Total number of time steps in calibration period.

In this study, the performance evaluation was conducted for a method I and II. Furthermore, the simulated discharge is divided into dry and wet period under method I and II and performance evaluation is executed.

4.14 Ranking of precipitation products

The ranking of precipitation product is done by allocating the score from 1 to 5 for precipitation product based on the performance result. For eg RMSE value of TRMM is lower or good performance than other products get the score 1 whereas the higher error or worst performance product get the score 5. Similarly, distribution of score to precipitation product based on performance obtained from different evaluation parameter and addition of the score of each precipitation products (Elagib and Mansell, 2000). The precipitation product that received lower sum score is ranked as number 1st. The ranking of a product is done for precipitation product under method I and II and based on wet (June-Oct) and dry (Nov-May) period under method I and II.

Chapter V

5 Results and discussions

5.1 Point to pixel rainfall comparison

The 43 ground-based stations are chosen for Nepal part of Koshi basin. Three stations are selected among 43 stations based on the lowest data gap and geo-physical division. The station Salleri lies in the Himalayan region, Chainpur located in the mountainous region whereas Chatara located in the Terai (plain) region. The point to pixel rainfall comparisons was done with visual observation and standard statistical analysis. The gauging data with the missing values are excluded from visual observation and statistical analysis. The results of the study are given below. The Aphrodite data are available until 2007 and other precipitation product data is available from 1998 to 2014. So, the analysis is done as per above mentioned time period.

5.1.1 Scatter plot of gauge vs satellite based precipitation products (SPPs)

Figure 12: Scatter plot of Salleri station rainfall vs satellite based precipitation products located at Himalayan region

Figure 13: Scatter plot of Chainpur (east) station rainfall vs satellite based precipitation products located at mountain region

Figure 14: Scatter plot of Chatara station rainfall vs satellite based precipitation products located at Terai region

In a Himalayan region as shown in Figure 12 predict the scatter plot of gauge precipitation against Aphrodite, TRMM, MSWEP and CMORPH products. It's elaborate that MSWEP and TRMM overestimate the rainfall values, CMORPH greatly underestimates the rainfall values, whereas Aphrodite slightly under-estimate the rainfall values but it shows a good estimation of peak rainfall values. The scatter plot in the mountain region shown in Figure 13 describe that diagonal line nearly divided the scatter plot for the products Aphrodite, MSWEP and TRMM. However, little overestimation of rainfall values is observed in MSWEP and TRMM product. The TRMM and MSWEP co-relation seems to be poor, while Aphrodite has good co-relation. The three products underestimate the rainfall values where Koshi enter into the plain area as shown in Figure 14. The higher value of the rainfall peak is recorded as 252.9mm/day, but corresponding precipitation products records 71.97mm/day in Aphrodite, 37.6mm/day in MSWEP, 35.6 mm/day in TRMM and 15.33 mm/day in CMORPH in Terai region respectively. In conclusion, CMORPH product greatly underestimated the rainfall values in all the three regions. It is observed that Aphrodite match the pattern of daily gauge precipitation whereas MSWEP, TRMM and CMORPH fail to do such.

5.1.2 Standard verification of satellite based precipitation products on daily basis

Four different statistical verification r^2 , RMSE, ME and MAE are carried out in the rainfall station that lies in the Himalayan, mountain and Terai region. The r^2 range from 0.15 to 0.84. The best co-relation is observed in Chatara station of Aphrodite product and worst performance is observed in 0.15 at Chainpur station of CMORPH product. The negative value of ME elaborates the underestimation of rainfall values that are noticed in CMORPH for all three stations with a value range from 2.01 mm/day to 3.19 mm/day. Similarly, the negative value of ME is observed at Salleri and Chatara station with a lesser amount in Aphrodite and TRMM products. The analysis shows that Aphrodite performs best in Chatara station in term of co-relation and predict good peak value in the mountain region as compared to other precipitation products. The MSWEP and TRMM products overestimate the rainfall value in Himalayan and mountain region and slightly underestimate the rainfall values at Terai region. The overall statistical performance is shown in Table 12 which elaborate that Aphrodite product performs better in all the region followed by MSWEP, TRMM and CMORPH product. Furthermore, more station should be put in analysis with lesser data gap, in order to conclude, which product is best suitable for given region.

Table 12: Standard verification of satellite based precipitation products on daily basis

Salleri Station				
Parameter	Aphrodite	MSWEP	TRMM	CMORPH
r^2	0.74	0.42	0.32	0.20
RMSE	6.62	11.70	12.22	10.36
ME	-0.55	1.78	-0.10	-3.19
MAE	3.16	5.84	5.65	4.88
Chainpur (east) Station				
r^2	0.77	0.38	0.22	0.15

Continue of Table 12

Parameter	Aphrodite	MSWEP	TRMM	CMORPH
RMSE	6.15	13.07	13.88	10.32
ME	1.03	3.60	1.70	-2.01
MAE	3.27	6.74	6.48	4.57
Chatara Station				
Parameter	Aphrodite	MSWEP	TRMM	CMORPH
r ²	0.82	0.47	0.28	0.24
RMSE	11.41	15.72	18.88	17.81
ME	-1.76	-0.83	-0.97	-2.93
MAE	3.97	6.46	7.53	6.71

5.1.3 Comparison of satellite based precipitation products on monthly basis

Figure 15: Monthly rainfall of Salleri station vs satellite based precipitation products located at Himalayan region

Figure 16: Monthly rainfall of Chainpur (east) station vs satellite based precipitation products located at mountain region

Figure 17: Monthly rainfall of Chatara station vs satellite based precipitation products located at Terai region

Continue of figure 17.

The monthly precipitation is calculated by accumulation of one month daily precipitation. The monthly precipitation period from 1998 to 2007 is considered for gauge and Aphrodite product and CMORPH, MSWEP and TRMM the period from 1998 to 2014 is taken because of availability of data. Figure 15 shows monthly precipitation in the Himalayan region which evaluate that TRMM and Aphrodite have good co-relation and slightly under-estimate the monthly peak rainfall. Conversely, the MSWEP overestimate the rainfall values at monthly peak and rest of the month follow nearly same. In mountain region, the Aphrodite, MSWEP and TRMM precipitation product overestimate the peak rainfall values than gauge precipitation as shown in Figure 16. But a different case is seen in the Terai region (Figure 17), where the precipitation products are underestimated by the gauge peaks value. The highest underestimation is observed in all the three regions for CMORPH product. The evaluation supports the strong effect of orography.

5.1.4 Monthly statistical verification of precipitation products

Standard verification technique is applied, to evaluate the performance of SPPs on the monthly basis on the station located at Himalaya, mountain and Terai region as shown in Table 13. The r^2 value for the Aphrodite, MSWEP, TRMM is almost 0.9 which indicate the good co-relation with gauge data. As compared with the NSE, Aphrodite product performs best, whose value range from 0.79 to 0.94 which shows the good relation in the monthly peak estimate. The ME error clearly elaborate that the recorded gauge precipitation is high in the Terai region compare to other precipitation products. The performance of the Aphrodite and TRMM is consistent in all the three regions but MSWEP performs poor in the mountain region. The statistical result suggests that the result might be useful to estimate the water balance estimation on monthly basis after correction of bias error for Aphrodite and TRMM products. As compared to the daily analysis the monthly performance is better.

Table 13: Monthly statistical verification of gauge rainfall vs satellite based precipitation products

Salleri Station				
Parameter	Aphrodite	MSWEP	TRMM	CMORPH
r ²	0.96	0.88	0.92	0.55
RMSE	55.21	110.46	71.63	181.54
ME	-16.33	53.18	-3.05	-95.15
MAE	30.36	72.86	40.33	109.95
NSE	0.94	0.77	0.90	0.37
Chainpur (east) Station				
Parameter	Aphrodite	MSWEP	TRMM	CMORPH
r ²	0.96	0.91	0.90	0.60
RMSE	84.17	149.73	95.97	116.57
ME	31.30	109.57	51.75	-61.08
MAE	35.49	110.56	62.09	74.27
NSE	0.79	0.26	0.70	0.55
Chatara Station				
Parameter	Aphrodite	MSWEP	TRMM	CMORPH
r ²	0.95	0.93	0.92	0.75
RMSE	95.05	104.99	95.44	177.19
ME	-53.08	-22.95	-27.20	-86.99
MAE	57.28	48.91	52.45	105.04
NSE	0.89	0.86	0.88	0.59

5.2 Optimization of model parameters

The J2000 model is the distributed which required 36 parameters for model simulation. The sensitivity test of 36 parameters was done. The sensitivity test was done by adjusting the different value of the parameter within in permissible range. The change of parameter by a small fraction that causes the change in simulation result significantly is known as a sensitive parameter. During sensitivity test process, very sensitive parameters are recession coefficient and threshold value for flood event, recession coefficient for overland and interflow, liner reduction coefficient for actual evapotranspiration (AET), flood routing coefficient and medium sensitive parameter are melt factor by sensible heat, liquid precipitation and soil heat flow, melt factor for ice melt, radiation melt factor for ice, debris factor for ice melt and soil maximum infiltration in summer and winter. The optimization of the parameter using the ground-based data and Aphrodite as main input is known as Method I optimization. The most suitable values for these parameters are given in Table 14. The final 36 parameter values which are finalized based on trial error and OPTAS optimization that is used in the model calibrating and validation. The letter written black colour is less sensitive, in blue colour are medium sensitive and red colour are a highly sensitive parameter. The optimization based on using individual precipitation products is known

as Method II optimization. The individual optimizes parameter under method II of individual precipitation products are listed in Annex 7.

Table 14: Calibration parameter for J2000 modelling under method I.

Parameters	Descriptions	Actual value	Range
PRECIP DISTRIBUTION			
Trs	base temperature	0	-1 to +1
Interception Module			
a_rain	interception storage for rain	1	0 to 5
a_snow	interception storage for snow	1.28	0 to 5
SNOW MODULE			
snowCritDens	critical density of Snow	0.381	0 to 1
snowColdContent (ccf_factor)	the cold content of the snowpack	0.0012	0 to 1
baseTemp	threshold temperature for snowmelt	0	-5 to 5
t_factor	melt factor by sensible heat	2.84	0 to 5
r_factor	melt factor by liquid precipitation	0.21	0 to 5
g_factor	melt factor by soil heat flow	3.73	0 to 5
GLACIER MODULE			
meltFactorIce	melt factor for ice melt	2.5	0 to 5
alphaIce	radiation melt factor for ice	0.2	0 to 5
kIce	routing co-efficient for ice melt	10	0 to 50
kSnow	routing co-efficient for snowmelt	5	0 to 50
kRain	routing co-efficient for rain runoff	5	0 to 50
debrisFactor	debris factor for ice melt	3	0 to 10
tbase	threshold temperature for snowmelt	-1	-5 to +5
SOIL MODULE			
soilMaxDPS	maximum depression storage	1	0 to 10
soilLinRed	linear reduction co-efficient for AET	0.55	0 to 10
soilMaxInfSummer	maximum infiltration in summer	18	0 to 200
soilMaxInfWinter	maximum infiltration in winter	114	0 to 200
soilMaxInfSnow	maximum infiltration in snow cover areas	10	0 to 200
soilImpGT80	infiltration for areas greater than 80% sealing	0.2	0 to 1
soilImpLT80	infiltration for areas lesser than 80% sealing	0.5	0 to 1
SoilDistMPSLPS	MPS-LPS distribution coefficient	0.27	0 to 10
SoilDiffMPSLPS	MPS-LPS diffusion coefficient	0.1	0 to 10
soilOutLPS	outflow coefficient for LPS	0.3	0 to 10
soilLatVertLPS	lateral vertical distribution coefficient	0.5	0 to 10

Continue of Table 14

Parameters	Descriptions	Actual value	Range
soilMaxPerc	maximum percolation rate to groundwater	10	0 to 100
soilConcRD1Flood	recession coefficient for flood event	1	0 to 10
soilConcRD1Floodthreshold	threshold value for soilConcRD1Flood	350	0 to 500
soilConcRD1	recession coefficient for overland flow	2.5	0 to 10
soilConcRD2	recession coefficient for Interflow	3.5	0 to 10
GROUNDWATER MODULE			
gwRG1RG2dist	RG1-RG2 distribution coefficient	2.1	0 to 5
gwRG1Fact	adaptation for RG1 flow	0.3	0 to 10
gwRG2Fact	adaptation for RG2 flow	0.5	0 to 10
gwCapRise	capillary rise coefficient	0.01	0 to 10
REACH ROUTING			
flowRouteTA	flood routing coefficient	3.8	0 to 10

(Note: The red letter represent most sensitive parameter, blue letter denote medium sensitive parameter and black letter represent less sensitive parameter)

5.3 Precipitation simulation in J2000 model

In this model, output precipitation simulation is categorized into rain and snow. The mean daily precipitation is calculated with IDW method. Calibration parameter base temperature (Trs) play the vital role in the amount of rain and snow products. The Trs value is assumed to be 0. The precipitation error such as moistening error, evaporation error and wind error is corrected as per (Richter, 1995) approach before IDW. The (groundbase+ Aphrodite) mean daily observed precipitation is compared with individual precipitation products. The elevation correction factor isn't used because of a low density of rain gauge station availability. The regionalization of the precipitation data is always the challenging job in a mountainous and Himalayan region because of the lower density of gauge network and variation in the spatial distribution of precipitation (Nepal, 2012). The mean daily gauge precipitation normally underestimates than actual because the most of the station lies in the valley and low elevation region which can't properly predict the precipitation value at a high mountain and Himalayan region. The underestimation of rainfall value is observed in Dudhkoshi and Tamor sub-basin which is part of Koshi basin. Such similar result is obtained in the study conducted by (Sharma, 1997). As per studied conducted on precipitation pattern distribution in Nepal, concluded that moderately high precipitation is observed in the Koshi region's high mountain and high Himalayan region (Kansakar et al., 2004). Also, the slope, aspect, wind facing and south facing slope plays important role in contributing localized precipitation patterns. These factors play a vital role in the assessment of water resource.

5.3.1 Daily statistical performance of simulated precipitation

The daily mean precipitation is compared on the basis of statistical performance and means daily simulation from 1998 to 2007 as shown in Table 15. The statistical performance shows that Aphrodite product has good performance with the gauge precipitation having r^2 value 0.96, RMSE value 1.09, ME value -0.52 , MAE value 0.59 and NSE value 0.94 respectively. The NSE and r^2 for TRMM are -0.39 and 0.33 and MSWEP have -0.42 and 0.57 respectively which indicate that precipitation product MSWEP performs poor in term of co-relation. Similarly, the positive value bias error reflects that products TRMM and MSWEP overestimate the rainfall values of 0.40 mm/day and 1.78mm/day respectively and negative value of 0.52 mm/day mean error of Aphrodite elaborate the slightly underestimate the rainfall value. However, the precipitation product Aphrodite perform best in term of correlation and bias error compare to other precipitation products.

Table 15: Daily statistical performance of simulated precipitation

Parameter	TRMM	Aphrodite	MSWEP	CMORPH
r^2	0.33	0.97	0.57	0.42
RMSE	5.22	1.05	5.29	4.68
ME	0.40	-0.52	1.78	-2.37
MAE	2.83	0.59	2.73	-2.37
NSE	-0.39	0.94	-0.42	-0.11

5.3.2 Average monthly simulated precipitation

The Figure 17 shows the monthly precipitation from the period Jan 1998 to Dec 2007 elaborate the good correlation of data on the dry period. However, the detailed analysis shows that TRMM products underestimate the rainfall values from (1 to 33) mm for 44 months period and overestimate the values from (1 to 125) mm in the period of 92 months. The minimum underestimation was observed in Sep-2002 and maximum overestimation is observed in the month April-1999. The analysis of Aphrodite product shows that majority of 90 months underestimate the rainfall values from (1 to 58) mm and rest of months shows nearly same the gauge values. The maximum underestimation is noticed in the month of July 2000. Generally, the underestimate is observed in the wet season from May to September. The MSWEP product overestimates the rainfall values in all the season and the maximum value of 252 mm was observed in the July 2007. In case of CMORPH, the monthly precipitation underestimate the rainfall values in all the month. This show that the TRMM and Aphrodite products precipitation simulation nearly match the gauge simulation.

Figure 17: Monthly gauge simulation vs satellite based precipitation products simulation in J2000 modelling

5.3.3 Average yearly precipitation

Figure 18 shows the average precipitation plot from 1998 to 2007 of gauge vs precipitation products on the daily basis. The underestimation of the TRMM precipitation is observed for 136 number of days which range from (0.11 to 5.41) mm. This underestimation is observed in the throughout the year. The overestimation is observed with a maximum value of 10.15 mm at 26 of July. The net yearly rainfall value is observed positive value. Aphrodite products overestimate the rainfall values to the negligible amount and underestimate the maximum rainfall values of 2.65 mm at 21 July. The MSWEP overestimate and CMORPOH underestimates the rainfall value throughout the year. The simulated average yearly gauge, TRMM, Aphrodite, MSWEP and CMORPH precipitation from the period of 1998 to 2007 is 1300, 1444, 1111, 1950 and 435 mm respectively.

Figure 18: Average daily simulated precipitation products from 1998 to 2007

5.4 Discharge simulation analysis

The J2000 model is calibrated from 1998 to 2002 and validation period is from 2003 to 2007 for gauge simulation discharge analysis and a period from 1998 to 2014 is considered for other precipitation products. The parameter set derived for the calibration is also used for the validation period. The analysis of simulation result is done in two ways. The first analysis is calibration and validation procedure using gauged and Aphrodite precipitation as main input datasets. The parameter developed for the (gauge and Aphrodite) simulation is used for simulation of discharge for the other precipitation products known as a method I and second analysis is calibration and validation procedure using individual precipitation products as main input is known as method II. The observed discharge in the Chatara station is compared with the simulation discharge both in calibration and validation period for both methods.

5.4.1 Gauge precipitation

A. Wet period

The wet period occurs from June to October of the year which is characterized by higher rainfall and discharge. The simulated flood peak underestimated by $58 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ to $536 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ in the calibration period and $312 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ to $2,455 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ in validation period. Figure 19 and 20 show the observed and simulated discharge during the calibration period (1998 to 2002) and validation period (2003 to 2007) of a gauge in the Koshi river basin. The overestimation of flood value is observed in the year 1999, 2001, 2004 and 2007. The maximum underestimation of a flood is observed in the year 2003 by $2,455 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ compare to observed discharge. The model predicts fairly in the flood peak exactly at 17 August 1999 and 9 July 2003. The corresponding precipitation observed at 17 August 1999 is 20.72 mm which is less than maximum precipitation occurs in that year. The flood peak occurs on that day may be due to water that stored in soil moisture release as interflow, percolation, ice melt and recession time of basin. The maximum peak flood simulation occurs on 25 July 2002 and has 27 leading days. The flood matches well in the year 1998 and 2002 compare to observed discharge. This is due to the high value of precipitation on that day which was distributed to all precipitation stations. The peak flood simulation has less than 5 days lead or lag time for the period of 7 years which is the good symbol to predict the peak flooding time.

B. Dry period

Figure 19: Observed and simulated discharge during the calibration period (1998-2002) of gauge in the Koshi river basin under method I (red line represent simulated runoff and blue line represent observed runoff).

The flow in the dry period is contributed by base water flow and ice melt. The snow and glacier melt parameter well predict streamflow character that especially occurs during April and May. The monsoon occurs from mid of June with high precipitation so it's difficult to differentiate the mixed runoff with ice melt. The snow and glacier melt depend upon several factors such as temperature, radiation, albedo, soil fluxes and energy balance etc. The pre-monsoon (March-May) and post-monsoon (October- November) period slightly overestimate the discharge value during the calibration period and slightly underestimate

during the validation period. The water in the unsaturated zone is depleted by evapotranspiration and interflow contribute to discharge as base flow. In the dry season (November to May), the most runoff is contributed by the saturated layer of groundwater as base flow and ice melt. The curve follows well both in a wet and dry period with slight underestimate and overestimates in the daily basis (shown in Figure 19 and 20). This trend shows that groundwater is stored during wet period and subsequent release during the dry period. The simulation well follows during raising and falling with slight underestimation and overestimation. This underestimation and overestimation might be due to an error in precipitation measurement, precipitation station located at a valley and low elevation, infiltration parameter, snow and glacier melting etc. value in the model. This also depends on how the parameters are optimized. As per Andermann *et al.* (2011), the evaluation of precipitation on the Himalayan fronts shows that basin-wide precipitation measurement is reduced from gauge data are significantly change if elevation is not covered by gauge stations and existing network in the Himalaya region is not sufficient to characterize orographic precipitation process accurately. Similarly, the simulated discharge produced in the Arc-SWAT model in the Dudh-Koshi basin is lower than observed discharge (Khadka, 2017). These results give clear views on effect of orography on discharge simulation.

Figure 20: Observed and simulated discharge during the validation period (2003-2007) of a gauge in the Koshi river basin under method I (red line represent simulated runoff and blue line represent observed runoff).

5.4.2 TRMM

Figure 21 shows the simulation runoff plot of TRMM products for the calibration period from 1998 to 2006 and Figure 22 show the validation period from 2007 to 2014 based on gauge calibration parameter. The maximum daily simulated discharge of $12,970 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ is recorded on 11 July 2004 and corresponding mean daily precipitation is 12.94 mm. The simulated discharge in raising limb and falling limb well fit during calibration period but with some overestimation during the dry period (November to May). In contrary, the simulated discharge underestimates in raising and falling limb during validation period and

slight overestimation during a dry period. The reason of underestimation may be less precipitation pixel value, the higher value of summer maximum infiltration, recession time for overland flow and a threshold value of flood or less value of ice melt factor causing lesser ice melt. The peak discharge is overestimated during the year 1998, 1999, 2001, 2002, 2004, 2005, 2006, 2007, 2011, 2012 and 2013. The simulation can't predict well during the flood period of the year 2003 and 2014. The reason behind may be TRMM product difficult to capture precipitation area with strong orographic effects. Similarly, study conducted on the Gandaki basin, Nepal with similar feature with Koshi basin by Kumar *et al.* (2016) supported that reliability of precipitation product depend upon the topography, in which TRMM product daily average overestimate the rain amount for low rain intensities over entire basin but underestimate high rain intensities over the high altitude mountainous areas. Bookhagen and Burbank (2010, 2006) predict that precipitation profile across the Himalayas greatly influences by topography.

Figure 21: Observed and simulated discharge during the calibration period (1998-2006) of TRMM product in the Koshi river basin under method I.

Figure 22: Observed and simulated discharge during the validation period (2007-2014) of TRMM product in the Koshi river basin under method I.

In the method II, the model is calibrated using the TRMM product as main input. By using the OPTAS optimization and hit and trial error, there is the slight improvement in the calibration efficiency but the validation efficiency remain the same. The rising and falling limbs well match than method I but only slight change with flood peak and lead or lag time. In this method, linear reduction coefficient for AET value is changed from 0.55 to 0.1 which cause the increase in the actual evapotranspiration and increased the value of threshold value of flood from 350 to 1500, and decreased in the recession coefficient for overland flow from 2.5 to 2 so that the dry period simulated flow is decreased. In addition, the peak can be improved in some adjustment in the model parameter but it may not represent real field condition. So the best approach may be improvement in the satellite orbits and sensor drift (Fisher *et al.*, 2013 and Brown *et al.*, 2009) and time dependence that are observed in the study of Krauker *et al.* (2013) in evaluation of TRMM bias precipitation in Nepal which can be mitigated by improvement in estimation algorithm. Furthermore, Muller and Thompson (2013), research on the bias adjustment of TRMM data through stochastic modelling in Nepal suggested the frequency domain bias correction. It may be useful for the water balance and estimation of flood peaks.

Figure 23: Observed and simulated discharge during a period (1998-2014) of TRMM product in the Koshi river basin under method II.

5.4.3 MSWEP

Figure 24 and 25 shows that MSWEP discharge simulation curve well follow the path parallel to observed discharge but with overestimation of discharge value. The simulation discharge is well predicted during the pre-monsoon and post-monsoon period. The highest peak flood is observed at the year 2004 with a discharge of $16,735\text{m}^3/\text{s}$ and corresponding precipitation of 37.5mm. The average

difference in discharge is $4,991 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. The monsoon flow prediction is too much higher due to the higher pixel value of precipitation estimate. This precipitation product seems to be unappropriated for discharge simulation and bias error should be corrected before using in hydrological modelling. To reduce such a higher simulation discharge some modification can be done within model parameter such as increasing the value of summer maximum infiltration, winter maximum infiltration, a threshold value for flood and recession coefficient for overland flow and the decreasing value of melt ice factor causing lesser ice melt and linear reduction coefficient for AET. Even though it can't predict the exact hydrological dynamic in that region in term of water balance but may be useful for predicting the flood peaks and estimation of higher probable flood for structure development works. A study conducted by Nair and Indu (2017) on India reveal that MSWEP precipitation overestimated the rainfall amount contribution rates in the middle rainfall class ranges ($3 \text{ mm/day} < \text{rainfall} < 20 \text{ mm/day}$) but underestimated it in the heavy rainfall class ($>50 \text{ mm/day}$). The point to pixel comparison of MSWEP suggested that it overestimate rainfall values at a mountain and Himalayan region and underestimate at the plain region during highest rainfall period. This symbolize the MSWEP have higher pixel value at a mountain, Himalaya and Tibetan region which cover more than 95 % of a study area.

Figure 24: Observed and simulated discharge during the calibration period (1998-2006) of MSWEP product in the Koshi river basin under method I.

Under method II, the individual calibration is obtained by decreasing the model parameter value in the melt factor by sensible heat, liquid precipitation, melt factor by soil heat flow, linear reduction coefficient for AET and increasing recession coefficient during a flood event and overland flow, debris factor for ice melt and maximum infiltration. This change makes the increase of NSE value from 0.20 to 0.34. The raising limb follows well but falling limbs overestimate the discharge value. As compare to a method I, there is less difference in the magnitude of the discharge and only discharge in the year 2004 underestimate the discharge value.

Figure 25: Observed and simulated discharge during the validation period (2007-2014) of MSWEP product in the Koshi river basin under method I.

Figure 26: Observed and simulated discharge during the period (1998-2014) of MSWEP product in the Koshi river basin under method II.

5.4.4 Aphrodite

Figure 27 and 28 show the Aphrodite simulation discharge during the calibration and validation period. The simulation discharge predicts well during a dry period but couldn't well predict during the wet season. During pre-monsoon and post-monsoon, the simulation discharge nearly equal to observed discharge but underestimate during the wet period. The peak simulated flood for the all period are lower

than observed peaks value expect at the year 1999 and 2004. This model predicts well for the timing of flood peak discharge for 6 number of year with lead or lag time less than 1 days. The simulated flood peak discharge is underestimated by 579 m³/s to 4,517 m³/s in given time series. The higher simulation is observed at the year 2004 with 7,699 m³/s discharge and corresponding 17.29 mm mean daily rainfall. As the Aphrodite product is derived from the gauge station data due to a limitation of rain gauge station at the higher elevation, it is unable to predict the hydrodynamic of that region. The main region behind the underestimation may be lower pixel value during monsoon, error in discharge measurement. In the bigger river like Koshi where a flood in the monsoon is too high some uncertainty may arise during stage-discharge rating curve which may not be efficient to compute the high flow discharge during a flood. Kattelmann (1987) reveals that rating curve of a Himalayan river has an inadequate number of the measurement.

Figure 27: Observed and simulated discharge during the calibration period (1998-2002) of Aphrodite product in the Koshi river basin under method I.

Figure 28: Observed and simulated discharge during the validation period (2003-2007) of Aphrodite product in the Koshi river basin under method I.

To improve the underestimation of flood peak, there is some modification in the model parameter. The model parameter such as linear reduction coefficient for AET is increased to reduce the evapotranspiration and parameter value such as maximum infiltration in summer, winter and snow cover area is decreased. The parameter such as recession coefficient for a flood event, overland flow and flow routing coefficient have higher effect in flood peak discharge whose value is increased to get better performance. By individual calibration, NSE value is increased from 0.68 to 0.77 and gap between the observed and simulated discharge are reduced. This calibration shows the good match of the curve during raising and falling limb and with slight overestimation during pre-monsoon period of the year 1999, 2000, 2002 and 2003. The underestimation by 22 m³/s to 3,218 m³/s and overestimation by 43 m³/s and 2430 m³/s is observed in the year 2001 and 2004 respectively. It predicts comparatively well during wet season than method I. This adjustment in the model parameter may not represent the real hydrodynamic feature in the field.

Figure 29: Observed and simulated discharge during the period (1998-2007) of Aphrodite product in the Koshi river basin under method II.

5.4.5 CMORPH

Figure 31 and 32 shows the discharge simulation of CMORPH product during calibration and validation period. It shows that discharge simulation is comparatively very much lower during calibration and validation period. The maximum simulated discharge is range from 314 m³/s to 1807 m³/s which is very much lower as compared with the peak observed discharge which in a range from 4,700 m³/s to 9,480 m³/s. The low estimation of discharge may be due to less pixel value of precipitation product.

Figure 30: Observed and simulated discharge during the calibration period (1998-2006) of CMORPH product in the Koshi river basin under method I.

Figure 31: Observed and simulated discharge during the validation period (2007-2014) of CMORPH product in the Koshi river basin under method I

In the second method, to increase the discharge, the evapotranspiration factor and recession time for flood event and overland flow are reduced and melting factor by sensible heat, liquid precipitation and soil heat flow are increased to promote more ice melt. Despite these change, it is unable to predict the flow behaviour and timing of the flooding. The only positive improvement is in the NSE value from 0.08 to 0.18. So, this product seems to be unappropriated for water balance and flood estimation. Similarly, the study conducted by Kumar *et al.* (2016) at Gandaki Basin of Nepal conclude that CMORPH entirely fails in capturing the higher rainfall intensity but does well with lower rainfall intensity. Guo *et al.* (2014) put light on the diurnal variation and the influential factors of CMORPH products reveal that the product fails to capture morning peaks and rainfall frequency solely depends upon the topography. Furthermore, the Krakauer, *et al.* (2013) strongly put the argument on CMORPH that greatly underestimated the mean

precipitation, and their elevation dependence of precipitation matched station observations poorly. This strongly recommended to do much for producing high spatial resolution and temporal coverage of geostationary satellites to improve precipitation estimates at fine scales with less latency especially in Himalayan and mountainous areas like Nepal where there is limited availability of ground data for calibration and validation in near real time.

Figure 32: Observed and simulated discharge during the period (1998-2014) of CMORPH product in the Koshi river basin under method II.

5.5 Comparison of peak discharges and lead or lag time

5.5.1 Based on method I

Table 16 shows the maximum peak floods and timing at which corresponding flood peak occurs from the year 1998 to 2014. The observed discharge shows flood occur in days of July and August based on yearly analysis. The maximum flood peak is observed at the year 2003 and corresponding flood peak for gauge, Aphrodite, MSWEP, TRMM and CMORPH are 7,024 m³/s, 10,709m³/s, 6,800m³/s and 369 m³/s respectively and timing of peak flood occurs at the 190th day for all the products expect Aphrodite whose timing is the 189th day. The minimum difference of 58.22 m³/s, 74.00 m³/s, 1,228.75m³/s, 26.64 m³/s, 314.57 m³/s and maximum difference of 2,455.82 m³/s, 4,517.02 m³/s, 10,775.42 m³/s, 7,010.11 m³/s and 1,695.72 m³/s is observed in the peak simulation of gauge, Aphrodite, MSWEP, TRMM and CMORPH respectively in given time series. The average peak simulation discharge difference are 766.43 m³/s, 1,494.52 m³/s, 4,991.93 m³/s, 2,409.11 m³/s, 5898.82 m³/s respectively observed in gauge, Aphrodite, MSWEP, TRMM and CMORPH. The timing of flood peaks of gauge, TRMM and Aphrodite nearly match the observed discharge timing. The average lead or lag timing that occurs in gauge, Aphrodite, MSWEP, TRMM and CMORPH having the average value of 6.8, 11.5, 16.6, 15.6 and 18.1 days respectively.

Table 16: Simulation of flood peak and lead or lag time under method I

Year	Observed Runoff	Day	Gauge		Aphrodite		MSWEP		TRMM		CMORPH	
	Max. Runoff		Max. Runoff	Lead or lag								
1998	6370	233	6303	-9	5146	0	8764	10	8756	-4	709	16
1999	6270	238	6674	0	6344	-54	14604	-54	10381	-25	786	31
2000	7540	215	7003	2	5546	1	11612	0	7567	6	315	3
2001	6500	232	7293	3	5949	3	11244	2	8844	0	473	47
2002	8780	233	8722	-27	7442	-27	14551	-30	10969	-29	1458	-28
2003	9480	190	7024	0	4963	1	10709	0	6800	0	369	0
2004	5960	192	7723	1	7699	1	16735	0	12970	0	958	0
2005	5630	232	5318	-5	4307	7	9313	-35	6605	-6	553	-11
2006	4700	238	4205	20	3095	20	7268	30	5933	30	1696	32
2007	6009	251	6789	1	5429	1	12358	-44	7145	-57	934	10
2008	5475	241					9163	-17	4971	-18	979	-17
2009	5494	231					10275	0	5299	-14	986	20
2010	7467	236					12207	-25	9320	-25	1220	-24
2011	5928	218					9370	0	6279	-18	1163	2
2012	5261	207					11940	-7	6252	-7	1807	40
2013	5549	191					9375	27	7567	25	1423	26
2014	6420	226					10403	1	4573	1	1242	1
Average lead or lag				6.8		11.5		16.6		15.6		18.1

(Note: -ve sign indicate the lagging days and +ve sign indicate the leading days, the unit of maximum runoff is m³/s and lead or lag time is day)

Table 17 shows the average discharge and corresponding flooding time at which the peak flood occurred. The average peak of 17 years shows that observed discharge occurs at 20August with the corresponding peak discharge of 4,756 m³/s. The timing of gauge and observed discharge shows that gauge lag by one day with the only overestimation by 125 m³/s of discharge which is lowest difference compare to other precipitation products. The highest difference in the peak flood estimation is observed in the MSWEP which is overestimated by 2,690 m³/s. Expect the gauge product, other precipitation products have peak flood lag or lead time from 14 to 24 days. The product CMORPH couldn't predict well with flooding value and timing.

Table 17: Average peak discharge and corresponding flooding time under method I.

SN	Product	Date	Peak discharge (m ³ /s)	Lead or lag (day)	Time period (year)
1	Gauge	21-Aug	4882	-1	10
2	TRMM	27-Jul	4986	24	17
3	Aphrodite	27-Jul	3818	24	10
4	MSWEP	30-Jul	7447	21	17
5	CMORPH	03-Sep	593	14	17
6	Observed	20-Aug	4757		17

(Note: -ve sign indicate the lagging days and +ve sign indicate the leading days)

5.5.2 Based on method II

Table 18: Simulation of flood peak and lead or lag time under method II.

Year	Observed Runoff		Aphrodite		MSWEP		TRMM		CMORPH	
	Max. Runoff	Day	Max. Runoff	Lead or lag						
1998	6370	233	6065	0	6647	13	7613	-1	2557	15
1999	6270	238	8107	-54	6415	-50	8393	-24	4876	-60
2000	7540	215	6147	1	7916	8	6934	12	2283	-101
2001	6500	232	6544	3	8036	6	7906	2	3202	-53
2002	8780	233	8107	-28	8841	-22	9182	-24	4269	-30
2003	9480	190	6261	1	7132	26	5990	22	3186	-13
2004	5960	192	8391	1	7947	5	8153	2	3301	-1
2005	5630	232	4974	7	6325	-2	5843	-5	5911	-13
2006	4700	238	3493	18	4989	6	4386	33	8885	29
2007	6009	251	5986	-2	9220	-36	5490	-16	4756	-74
2008	5475	241			6951	-13	4597	-18	4007	-42
2009	5494	231			7159	2	4448	-20	5752	10
2010	7467	236			8130	3	6428	-23	9852	-93
2011	5928	218			7023	21	5436	2	7995	-80
2012	5261	207			7532	1	4331	2	8980	38
2013	5549	191			6810	37	5821	26	6606	-45
2014	6420	226			5987	7	3777	2	8120	-105
				11.50		15.18		13.76		47.18

(Note: -ve sign indicate the lagging days and +ve sign indicate the leading days, the unit of maximum runoff is m³/s and lead or lag time is day)

When the model is calibrated based on the individual precipitation products as main input, the gap between observed and simulation are highly minimized. Table 18 shows the simulation of flood peak and lead or lag time under method II for time period from 1998 to 2014. The average differences in the peak simulation discharge are 1,178.78 m³/s, 1,092.61 m³/s, 1,250.78 m³/s and 3,294.41 m³/s that are observed in Aphrodite, MSWEP, TRMM and CMORPH respectively. The CMORPH simulation peak tries to follow the flood peak but fails to follow the discharge simulation pattern during all round year with an unappropriated timing of flooding in which lead or lag time varies from 1 to 105 days. There is no considerable improvement in the flood timing which occur similar to method I. It seems as gauge simulation nearly match, Aphrodite slightly underestimate, MSWEP highly overestimate, TRMM slightly overestimate and CMORPH highly underestimate the flood peaks simulation. The TRMM and MSWEP after bias correction may be used for flood modelling. This maximum flood and corresponding lead or lag time help for flood forecast, its frequency, timing and occurrence. It helps to policymaker to think for a structural or non-structural measure to mitigate such effect. Accurate rainfall estimation and optimum model calibration play a vital role in reliable flood modelling and warning system.

Table 19: Average peak discharge and corresponding flooding time under method II.

SN	Product	Date	Peak discharge (m ³ /s)	Lead or lag (day)	Time period (year)
1	TRMM	30-Jul	4597.24	21	17
2	Aphrodite	27-Jul	4325.39	24	10
3	MSWEP	26-Aug	6210.19	-6	17
4	CMORPH	01-May	1525.78	111	17
5	Observed	20-Aug	4757		17

(Note: -ve sign indicate the lagging days and +ve sign indicate the leading days.)

Table 19 shows the average peak discharge and corresponding flooding time under method II. This show the improvement of peak discharge compare to method I. The abundant improvement in the peak flood timing is only observed in MSWEP product. In addition, the CMORPH improved in peak simulation compare to the method I but worst flood timing is accounted. This recommends the individual calibration of precipitation products after correction of bias error may provide reliable flood peak modelling.

5.6 Statistical performance of precipitation products

5.6.1 Based on method I

Table 20 shows the statistical performance of precipitation products under the method I based on calibration and validation period. As per statistical performance the Aphrodite product perform best followed by TRMM, MSWEP and CMORPH respectively. Overall, the model perform well expect for MSWEP and CMORPH. NSE range from (0.01 to 0.76) in calibration (Cali.) and (0.12 to 0.80) in validation (Vali.) period. In NSE calculation, the difference value are square, so it is more sensitive

during high flow period. To address these issue the modified form of Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (Modified NSE) is introduced by not taking square value and only the absolute difference is taken. In term of Modified NSE parameter, Aphrodite product perform best followed by TRMM but in contrary, the MSWEP and CMORPH perform worse which indicate that MSWEP and CMORPH fail to capture hydrodynamic of that region during low flow period. The r^2 value is above 0.80 expect the product CMORPH. Even though MSWEP product have the r^2 value 0.87 in calibration and 0.90 in validation indicate MSWEP simulation follow pattern of observed discharge. But in reality the MSWEP simulation overestimate the discharge value by following parallel path above observed discharge. The average volume error (AVE) range from 0.10 to 0.86. The near accurate simulation of discharge is estimated in gauge and worst estimation is observed in the CMORPH. The PBIAS error give the general overview in overestimation and underestimation of simulation of discharge value during calibration and validation period. The underestimation from (4.25 to 85.67) % of discharge and (9.91 to 75) % overestimation of simulation discharge is estimated during the study under the Method I. The overall PBIAS is lower in case of gauge followed by TRMM, Aphrodite, MSWEP and CMORPH respectively. The peak error elaborate the difference between observed and simulated flood peak in the given time series. The negative value of peak error indicate the overestimation of simulated peak and positive value indicate underestimation of simulation peak. During the calibration period, the gauge product has least peak error of 0.087 and during validation period, Aphrodite and MSWEP has least peak error of -0.030 . Wave error compare the each difference in observed and simulated discharge value in reference with the maximum observed flood peaks in given time series. The TRMM simulation shows the least wave error of -0.020 and 0.008 , during calibration and validation period respectively.

Table 20: Statistical performance of precipitation products under the method I

SN	Parameter	Gauge		Aphrodite		MSWEP		TRMM		CMORPH	
		Cali.	Vali.	Cali.	Vali.	Cali.	Vali.	Cali.	Vali.	Cali.	Vali.
1	NSE	0.76	0.80	0.73	0.63	0.27	0.12	0.64	0.73	-0.01	0.20
2	Modified NSE	0.90	0.89	0.86	0.71	0.17	-0.24	0.75	0.83	-0.55	-0.21
3	r^2	0.92	0.91	0.89	0.87	0.87	0.90	0.81	0.83	0.26	0.41
4	AVE	0.10	0.10	0.15	0.30	0.61	0.75	0.13	0.04	0.86	0.64
5	RMSE	484.32	535.17	587.45	863.62	1456.43	1574.48	798.09	583.98	1992.54	1551.98
6	PBIAS	9.91	-9.79	-14.56	-29.96	61.16	75.00	12.97	-4.25	-85.67	-63.50
7	Wave error	-0.02	0.02	0.04	0.06	-0.10	-0.14	-0.02	0.01	0.13	0.12
8	Peak error	0.09	-0.03	0.27	-0.03	0.27	-0.03	-0.27	-0.20	4.59	3.13

5.6.2 Based on method II

Similarly, Table 21 shows the statistical performance of precipitation products under the method II based on calibration and validation period. The method II shows the improvement of the performance

efficiency in each of the precipitation product. There is little change in NSE value in the method of Aphrodite and TRMM product but MSWEP and CMORPH product NSE value are increased by (12 to 15) percentage. There is an improvement in a parameter such as NSE, modified NSE, r^2 , RMSE, peak error for all the products but error such as wave error increased from 0.01 to 0.21. There is considerably increased improvement of wave error of CMORPH both in calibration and validation. This result put in the light that simulated flood peak and observed flood peaks get increased and follow the good pattern of simulated discharge.

Table 21: Statistical performance of precipitation products under the method II

SN	Parameter	Aphrodite		MSWEP		TRMM		CMORPH	
		Cali.	Vali.	Cali.	Vali.	Cali.	Vali.	Cali.	Vali.
1	NSE	0.79	0.74	0.39	0.28	0.66	0.72	0.15	0.22
2	Modified NSE	0.92	0.84	0.50	0.26	0.78	0.82	-0.27	-0.06
3	r^2	0.92	0.90	0.83	0.88	0.81	0.83	0.15	0.08
4	AVE	0.00	0.15	0.46	0.60	0.09	0.09	0.68	0.34
5	RMS	441	639	1132	1213	756	595	1803	1455
6	PBIAS	-0.11	-15.48	45.63	59.62	8.80	-8.82	-68.00	-34.16
7	Wave error	-0.17	0.03	-0.07	-0.11	-0.01	0.02	0.11	0.06
8	Peak error	0.17	-0.11	0.17	-0.11	0.03	0.16	0.07	-0.24

5.7 Comparison of performance evaluation with other studies

Table 22: Streamflow calibration and validation statistical performance at Chatara station

SN	Model	Calibration			Validation		
		Period	PBIAS	NSE	Period	PBIAS	NSE
1	GR4JSG (Penton et al., 2016)	1996-2003	9.80	0.82	1998-2007	10.90	0.81
					2005-2009	15.10	0.80
					2001-2005	3.80	0.83
2	SWAT (IWMI, 2013)	2001-2004	8.70	0.83	2005-2009	-13.80	0.80
3	SPHY (Lutz et al., 2014)	1998-2007	7.90	0.87			
4	SWAT (Bharati et al., 2012)	1996-2000		0.62	2001-2005		0.81
5	J2000 (this study)Gauge	1998-2002	9.91	0.76	2003-2007	-9.79	0.80

Source: adapted from (Penton et al., 2016)

Table 22 shows a statistical performance of simulation discharge during calibration and validation period at Chatara station. Penton *et al.* (2016) used the calibration period from 1996 to 2003 and validated simulation flow in three periods. They used the ESDIIM data set up to 3000m elevation and WATCH data set in the elevation higher than 3000m. It reveals that NSE value range from 0.80 to 0.83 and overestimation of simulation discharge both in calibration and validation.

The study conducted by Bhatati *et al.* (2012) used the GCMs to generate the daily climate data CNRM-CM3, CSIRO-Mk3.5, ECHam5, and MIROC3.2 and data used in SWAT hydrological modelling, is projected data that are average from these four GCMs. The NSE value in the calibration and validation period is 0.62 and 0.81 respectively. IWMI (2013) use SWAT model and Lutz *et al.* (2014) use SPHY model, analyses similar disparity in flow simulation. The main reason for the disparity may be due to an error in rainfall value, calibration of model parameter and recording in observed discharge. As compare the NSE value with past studies the NSE value is similar and PBIAS error is positive during calibration in all method and positive in other studies expect in this study and IWMI (2013).

5.8 Ranking and statistical performance of precipitation products

Table 23: Ranking and statistical performance of precipitation products under method I.

SN	Parameter	Gauge		Aphrodite		MSWEP		TRMM		CMORPH	
		Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank
1	NSE	0.78	1	0.68	2	0.20	3	0.68	2	0.08	4
2	Modified NSE	0.90	1	0.78	2	0.01	3	0.78	2	-0.41	4
3	r ²	0.90	1	0.86	3	0.87	2	0.81	4	0.18	5
4	AVE	0.00	1	0.22	3	0.67	4	0.05	2	0.76	5
5	RMSE	510.38	1	738.55	2	1512.35	4	706.86	3	1801.58	5
6	PBIAS	-0.11	1	-22.40	3	67.30	4	5.32	2	-75.83	5
7	Wave error	0.000	1	0.035	3	-0.104	4	-0.009	2	0.113	5
8	Peak error	0.087	1	0.231	3	0.231	3	-0.269	2	4.245	4
9	Sum rank		8		21		27		19		37
	Final rank		1st		3rd		4th		2nd		5th

The Table 23 and 24 show the statistical performance and ranking of the precipitation products under method I and II respectively. The 1 rank value is given in the method of best performance followed by value 2, 3, 4 and 5 for least performance. The rank value of each parameter is sum at the end under method I and II. The total rank value under the method I for the gauge, Aphrodite, MSWEP, TRMM and CMORPH products are 8, 21, 27, 19 and 37 respectively. Similarly, the total rank value considering the method II for Aphrodite, MSWEP, TRMM and CMORPH products are 13, 24, 13 and 29 respectively. In the method I, the gauge get least rank value of 8 so it is rank as 1st which is followed by TRMM, Aphrodite, MSWEP and CMORPH respectively. Furthermore, under the method II, Aphrodite and TRMM get equal rank value but the most important statistical parameter of NSE value of Aphrodite is greater than TRMM, so the Aphrodite is rank as 1st, TRMM as 2nd, MSWEP as 3rd and CMORPH as the last rank.

Table 24: Ranking and statistical performance of precipitation products under method II.

SN	Parameter	Aphrodite		MSWEP		TRMM		CMORPH	
		Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank
1	NSE	0.77	1	0.34	3	0.69	2	0.18	4
2	Modified NSE	0.88	1	0.41	3	0.80	2	-0.18	4
3	r ²	0.90	1	0.84	2	0.81	3	0.08	4
4	AVE	0.08	2	0.52	3	0.01	1	0.53	4
5	RMSE	548.72	1	1170.07	3	686.10	2	1650.79	4
6	PBIAS	-7.93	2	51.84	3	0.98	1	-52.98	4
7	Wave error	0.01	2	-0.08	4	0.00	1	0.08	3
8	Peak error	0.13	3	0.13	3	0.03	1	-0.04	2
	Sum rank		13		24		13		29
	Final rank		1st		3rd		2nd		4th

5.9 Statistical performance and ranking based on season

5.9.1 Based on wet and dry season under method I

Table 25: Statistical performance and ranking during wet period under method I.

SN	Parameter	Gauge		Aphrodite		TRMM		MSWEP		CMORPH	
		Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank
1	NSE	0.76	1	0.49	2	0.48	3	-1.36	4	-2.48	5
2	Modified NSE	0.36	2	0.36	2	0.39	1	-0.51	3	-0.93	4
3	r ²	0.77	1	0.73	2	0.65	4	0.72	3	0.08	5
4	AVE	0.19	1	0.28	2	0.26	3	0.65	4	0.83	5
5	RMSE	768.37	1	1125.88	3	1068.62	2	2273.45	4	2760.13	5
6	PBIAS	-0.02	2	-0.26	3	0.01	1	0.64	4	-0.83	5
7	Wave error	0.01	1	0.08	2	-0.01	1	-0.15	3	0.21	4
8	Peak error	0.09	1	0.23	2	-0.43	3	-0.43	3	4.24	4
	Sum rank		10		18		18		28		37
	Final rank		1st		2nd		3rd		4th		5th

The Table 25 and 26 elaborate the statistical performance was done dividing the simulation discharge into the wet (June-Oct) and dry (Nov-May) period. The results of statistical performance as shown in Table 25 reveal that NSE values are decreased in all product because the difference in the observed mean and observed discharge get reduced. The NSE value shows a satisfactory result for gauge, Aphrodite in a dry season and wet season. Furthermore, NSE value for TRMM for the wet season show satisfactory

result but show poor performance during the dry season. This means the error prediction range is decreased. All the product shows the good coefficient of correlation expects the product CMORPH. CMORPH unable to follow the pattern of discharge simulation. When we compare the dry and wet period simulation, the wet period simulation perform better but RMSE value in the wet season is greater than dry season. The overall discharge simulation of TRMM during a wet period can be applied in the estimation of water balance because the PBIAS error is only 1 to 3 %. The PBIAS error of CMORPH and MSWEP is considerably high in both dry and wet period. The wave error in gauge, Aphrodite and CMORPH shows the positive value in a range from 1 to 21% in a wet period which symbolizes underestimation of discharge value during the wet period. Conversely, the negative value of wave error is calculated for gauge during a dry period. The highest value of peak error 4.24 and 1.96 observed in CMORPH and lowest value of peak error -0.07 and 0.09 is observed in gauge product both in dry and wet season respectively. The ranking of precipitation products at wet season shows that gauge precipitation perform best followed by Aphrodite, TRMM, MSWEP and CMORPH respectively and in dry season ranking the first three ranking position is same as the wet season with the interchanging of ranking between CMORPH and MSWEP only.

Table 26: Statistical performance and ranking during dry period under method I

SN	Parameter	Gauge		Aphrodite		TRMM		MSWEP		CMORPH	
		Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank
1	NSE	0.45	1	0.4	2	-0.03	3	-4.87	5	-1.73	4
2	Modified NSE	0.34	1	0.34	1	0	2	-1.65	4	-0.8	3
3	r ²	0.61	1	0.43	4	0.53	3	0.6	2	0.01	5
4	AVE	0.2	1	0.21	2	0.31	3	0.83	5	0.56	4
5	RMSE	150.39	1	157.43	2	193.58	3	462.39	5	315.14	4
6	PBIAS	0.07	2	-0.06	1	0.25	3	0.82	5	-0.41	4
7	Wave error	-0.02	1	0.02	1	-0.04	2	-0.14	4	0.07	3
8	Peak error	-0.07	1	1.04	3	-0.44	2	-0.44	2	1.96	4
	Sum rank		9		16		21		32		31
	Final rank		1st		2nd		3rd		5th		4th

5.9.2 Based on wet and dry season under method II

The Table 27 and 28 show statistical performance under method II for wet and dry season. The result in the dry and wet season shows that there is an improvement in the performance efficiency of all the product. Similar to a method I, the correlation of TRMM and Aphrodite predict well as compared with observed discharge and MSWEP and CMORPH fail to predict simulation discharge. So individual simulation prove that the precipitation products that are simulated individually perform better than calibration based on gauge parameter but it might not represent real hydrodynamic of a region. As per

statistical performance, the Aphrodite product is rank as first, TRMM as second, MSWEP as third and CMORPH as last. So overall analysis shows that Aphrodite product performs best but it has the disadvantage of data availability only up to the year 2007.

Table 27: Statistical performance and ranking under method II during wet period

SN	Parameter	Aphrodite		TRMM		MSWEP		CMORPH	
		Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank
1	NSE	0.72	1	0.51	2	-0.39	3	-1.80	4
2	Modified NSE	0.56	1	0.38	2	-0.21	3	-0.66	4
3	r ²	0.78	1	0.61	3	0.63	2	0.02	4
4	AVE	0.19	1	0.27	2	0.52	3	0.72	4
5	RMSE	832.06	1	1039.07	2	1747.46	3	2476.45	4
6	PBIAS	-0.13	2	-0.03	1	0.48	3	-0.69	4
7	Wave error	0.04	2	0.0005	1	-0.11	3	0.18	4
8	Peak error	0.13	3	0.03	1	0.03	1	0.06	2
	Sum rank		12		14		21		30
	Final rank		1st		2nd		3rd		4th

Table 28: Statistical performance and ranking under method II during dry period

SN	Parameter	Aphrodite		TRMM		MSWEP		CMORPH	
		Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank
1	NSE	0.54	1	0.11	2	-3.31	3	-6.50	4
2	Modified NSE	0.34	1	0.10	2	-1.34	4	-1.04	3
3	r ²	0.65	1	0.51	3	0.60	2	0.00	4
4	AVE	0.21	1	0.28	2	0.73	4	0.64	3
5	RMSE	137.87	1	180.44	2	396.10	3	522.53	4
6	PBIAS	0.14	1	0.18	2	0.71	4	0.20	3
7	Wave error	-0.0328	2	-0.0314	1	-0.1219	4	-0.0342	3
8	Peak error	0.4728	2	-0.0355	1	-0.0355	1	-0.7370	3
	Sum rank		10		15		25		27
	Final rank		1st		2nd		3rd		4th

CHAPTER VI

6 Conclusions and recommendations

6.1 Conclusions

Satellite precipitation plays a vital role when there is no rainfall station and coverage is lower. But the estimate from the satellite observation contains errors and bias because of the indirect nature of the relationship between the observation and the precipitation, the inadequate sampling and algorithm imperfections (Xie *et.al*, 2002). Errors in precipitation estimation can bring significant uncertainties in stream flow simulation and prediction (Sorooshian *et al.*, 2011). So, it should be verified scientifically before practical application. For this purpose, the Koshi basin upstream of Chatara climate station which lies in the Tibetan and Nepal parts are taken as a study area. The precipitation products Aphrodite, TRMM, MSWEP and CMORPH are selected based on the performance of these products in the similar climatically and geographical that are explained on literature. The precipitation products are evaluated in two ways. One is a point to pixel rainfall comparison and other is using J2000 rainfall-runoff model based on simulation of discharge compared with observed discharge. Different input data set such as rain, temperature, wind, sunshine duration, relative humidity and parameter files such as HRUs, reaches, soil, land use, geology are collected from different source or developed using different tools such as such as Arc GIS, QGIS, Hydrus1D.4xx, HWSO viewer, R and Python script for model initialization. A total 12,661 units of HRUs and 342 reaches are delineated which represented the spatial heterogeneity of the basin. Two methods are employed to evaluate the precipitation products on J2000 model. In the method I, the model is calibrated based on gauge precipitation as the main input and other precipitation products are evaluated based on gauge calibration parameter and method II involve the individual calibration of precipitation products as the main input and the performance are carried out simultaneously.

During point to pixel rainfall comparison of gauge vs SPPs, the 3 stations (Salleri, Chainpur and Chatara) that lies in three distinct geographical regions such as Himalayan, mountain and Terai region are chosen based on the lowest data gap. In Himalayan region scatter plot shows that MSWEP and TRMM overestimate the rainfall values, CMORPH greatly underestimates the rainfall values, whereas Aphrodite slightly under-estimate the rainfall values but it shows a good estimation during wet period. In the mountain region, little overestimation of rainfall values is observed in MSWEP and TRMM product and all products underestimate the rainfall values where Koshi enter into the plain area.

The daily and monthly statistical performance reveal that Aphrodite product has highest performance efficiency compare to other products. The overall statistical parameter indicates that Aphrodite product performs better in all the regions followed by MSWEP, TRMM and CMORPH product. When the analysis is done on the monthly basis the statistical performance gets improved. In Himalayan region, TRMM and Aphrodite have good co-relation and slightly under-estimate the monthly peak rainfall. Conversely, the MSWEP overestimate the rainfall values at monthly peak rainfall and rest of the month follow nearly same. In mountain region, the TRMM, Aphrodite and MSWEP product overestimate the

peak rainfall values than gauge precipitation. But the different case was seen in the Terai region, where the precipitation products underestimate the rainfall peaks value. The high underestimation is observed in all the three regions for CMORPH product. This supports the strong effect of orography, slope, aspect etc. However, more station should be put in analysis with lesser data gap, in order to conclude, which product is best suitable for given region.

The main objective of this study is to evaluate the performance of ground data and satellite-based precipitation products on J2000 modelling. The statistical performance of mean daily precipitation simulations shows that Aphrodite product has good performance with NSE value 0.94 and other SPPs TRMM, MSWEP and CMORPH have negative NSE values of 0.39, 0.42 and 0.11 respectively. Similarly, the positive value bias error reflect that products TRMM and MSWEP overestimate the rainfall values, CMORPH greatly underestimates and Aphrodite slightly underestimates the rainfall value. The mean daily gauge precipitation normally underestimates than actual because the most of the station lies in the valley and low elevation region which can't properly predict the precipitation value at a high mountain and Himalayan region. As per studied conducted on precipitation pattern distribution in Nepal, concluded that moderately high precipitation is observed in the Koshi region's high mountain and high Himalayan region (Kansakar *et al.*, 2004).

The J2000 model is calibrated from 1998 to 2002 and validation period is from 2003 to 2007 for (gauge+Aphrodite) simulation discharge analysis and a period from 1998 to 2006 for calibration and 2007 to 2014 is considered for other precipitation products. The pixel value of rainfall and model parameters play a vital role in discharge simulation. There are 36 distinct model parameters in J2000 modelling. During sensitivity test process, very sensitive parameters are recession coefficient for flood event, threshold value for flood event, recession coefficient for overland flow, recession coefficient for interflow, flood routing coefficient and medium sensitive parameter are melt factor by sensible heat, liquid precipitation, soil heat flow, melt factor for ice melt, radiation melt factor for ice, debris factor for ice melt, summer and winter maximum infiltration. The parameters in the model are optimized before validation. The model is calibrated and validated inputting the ground gauge & Aphrodite (for Tibetan part) as main input based on the principle of split sample test. The same calibrated parameter including all the input and parameter file expects rain is used to run the model for the 4 precipitation products simultaneously known as method I. Again the model is calibrated based on individual SPPs as main input and validation are carried out known as method II.

Following conclusion are drawn during calibration and validation under method I.

1. The gauge simulated flood peak is underestimated by 58 m³/s to 536 m³/s in the calibration period and 312 m³/s to 2,455 m³/s in validation period. The overestimation of flood value is observed in the year 1999, 2001, 2004 and 2007. The flow in the dry period is contributed by base water flow and ice melt. The snow and glacier melt parameter well predict streamflow character that especially occurs during April and May. The monsoon occurs from mid of June with high precipitation so it's difficult to differentiate the mixed runoff with ice melt. The snow and glacier melt depend upon several factors such as temperature, radiation, albedo, soil fluxes and energy balance etc. The pre-monsoon (March-May)

and post-monsoon (October- November) period slightly overestimate the discharge value during the calibration period and slightly underestimate during the validation period.

2. The TRMM simulated discharge in raising limb and falling limb well fit during calibration period but with some overestimation during the dry period (November to May). In contrary, the simulated discharge underestimates in raising and falling limb during validation period and slight overestimation during a dry period. The reason of underestimation may be less precipitation pixel value, a higher value of summer maximum infiltration, a threshold value for flood and recession coefficient for overland flow and the decreasing value of melt factor for ice causing lesser ice melt.
3. The MSWEP simulation curve well follows the path parallel to observed discharge but with overestimation of discharge value. To reduce such a higher simulation discharge some modification can be done within model parameter such as increasing the value of summer maximum infiltration, winter maximum infiltration, a threshold value for flood and recession coefficient for overland flow and the decreasing value of melt ice factor causing lesser ice melt and linear reduction coefficient for AET. Even though it can't predict the exact hydrological dynamic in that region in term of water accounting but may be useful for predicting the flood peaks and higher probable flood in the future for structure development works and non-structural flood mitigation.
4. The Aphrodite simulation discharge predicts well during a dry period but couldn't well predict during the flood peaks. During pre-monsoon and post-monsoon, the simulation discharge nearly equal to observed discharge but underestimate during the flood period. The main region behind the underestimation may be lower pixel value during monsoon, error in discharge measurement. In the bigger river like Koshi where a flood in the monsoon is too high some uncertainty may arise during stage-discharge rating curve which may not be efficient to compute the high flow discharge during a flood. Kattelmann (1987), reveal that rating curve of the Himalayan river has an inadequate number of the measurement.
5. CMORPH discharge simulation is comparatively very much lower during calibration and validation period. Tian and Peters-Lidard (2010) suggest the improvement in the sensor algorithms for mountainous regions, where terrain changes on short distances and have high orographic influence. This strongly recommended to do much for producing high spatial resolution and temporal coverage of geostationary satellites to improve precipitation estimates at fine scales with less latency especially in Himalayan and mountainous areas like Nepal where there is limited availability of ground data for calibration and validation in near real time.

Under the method I the statistical performance shows that gauge, Aphrodite, TRMM, MSWEP and CMORPH have the NSE and PBIAS value of (0.78 and -0.11%), (0.68 and -22.40%), (0.62 and 5.32%), (0.20 and 67.30%) and (0.08 and -75.83%) respectively. The peak discharge estimation shows

that flood occurs in days of July and August. The average peak simulation discharge difference are 766.43 m³/s, 1,494.52 m³/s, 4,991.93 m³/s, 2,409.11 m³/s, 5,898.82 m³/s respectively observed in gauge, Aphrodite, MSWEP, TRMM and CMORPH. The timing of flood peaks of gauge, TRMM and Aphrodite nearly match the observed discharge timing. The average lead or lag timing that occurs in gauge, Aphrodite, TRMM, MSWEP and CMORPH having an average value of 6.8, 11.5, 15.6, 16.6 and 18.1 days respectively. The statistical performance was also done dividing the simulation discharge into the wet (June-Oct) and dry (Nov-May) period. The result of statistical performance shows that NSE is decreased in all product because the difference in the simulated discharge and observed discharge get reduced. The ranking of precipitation products under the method I, has the gauge as 1st rank followed by TRMM in 2nd rank, Aphrodite in 3rd rank, MSWEP in 4th rank and CMORPH in the last rank. The ranking of precipitation products at wet season shows that gauge precipitation perform best followed by Aphrodite, TRMM, MSWEP and CMORPH respectively and in dry season ranking, the first three ranking are same as a wet season with the interchanging of ranking between CMORPH and MSWEP only.

The conclusions that are drawn simulation under method II are listed below.

1. In the TRMM individual simulation analysis, rising and falling limbs well match than I method but only slight change with flood peak and lead or lag time. In addition, the wet flow is improved in some adjustment in the model parameter but it may not represent real field condition. So the best approach may be improvement in the satellite orbits and sensor drift (Fisher *et al.*, 2013 and Brown *et al.*, 2009) and time dependence that are observed in the study of Krauker *et al.* (2013) in evaluation of TRMM bias precipitation in Nepal which can be mitigated by improvement in estimation algorithm. Furthermore, Muller and Thompson (2013), research on the bias adjustment of TRMM data through stochastic modelling in Nepal suggested the frequency domain bias correction. It may be useful for the water balance and estimation of flood peaks after correction of bias error.
2. The individual calibration of MSWEP product improves in NSE value from 0.20 to 0.34. The raising limb follows well but falling limbs overestimate the discharge value. As compare to a method I, there is less difference in the gap between the discharge at observed flood peaks and flood peak simulation and only discharge at the year 2004 underestimate the discharge value. The point to pixel rainfall comparison of MSWEP suggested that it overestimate rainfall values at a mountain and Himalayan region and underestimate at the plain region during highest rainfall period. This symbolize the MSWEP have higher pixel value at the mountain, Himalaya and Tibetan region which cover more than 95 % of a study area.
3. In the CMORPH simulation, it fails to predict the pattern of observed discharge even though it has some increase in the efficiency of NSE from 0.20 to 0.34. As compared to a method I, there is less difference in the gap between the discharge at high flood and flood peak simulation but completely fail to estimate the timing of peak floods.

4. By individual Aphrodite calibration, NSE value is increased from 0.68 to 0.77 and gap between the observed and simulated discharge are reduced. It predicts comparatively well during wet season than method I. This product might be the best alternative for water balance estimation where there isn't rainfall station and the establishment of rain gauge is economically and physically not feasible.

Under the method II, when the precipitation products have individually calibrated the gap between observed and simulated discharge is considerably reduced resulting in improved model efficiency. The products Aphrodite, TRMM, MSWEP and CMORPH have increased NSE values from (0.68 to 0.77), (0.62 to 0.69), (0.20 to 0.40) and (0.08 to 0.18) respectively and decreased values of PBIAS from (22.40 to -7.93 %), (5.32 to 0.98) %, (67.30 to 51.84) % and (-75.83 to -52.98) % respectively. The average difference in the peak simulation discharge are 1,178.78 m³/s, 1092.61 m³/s, 1,250.78 m³/s, and 3,294.41 m³/s that are observed in Aphrodite, MSWEP, TRMM and CMORPH respectively which is comparatively less than method I. The CMORPH simulation peak try to follow the flood peak but fail to follow the discharge simulation during all round year with unappropriated timing of flood peak, in which lead or lag time varies from 1 to 105 days. There is no considerable improvement in the flood timing compare to method I. The statistical performance of wet and dry period show good performance compare to a method I seasonal analysis. The ranking of precipitation product under method II, wet and dry period shows that Aphrodite products perform best and followed by TRMM, MSWEP and CMORPH respectively.

In conclusion, the gauge simulation nearly match, Aphrodite slightly underestimate, MSWEP highly overestimates, TRMM slightly overestimates and CMORPH highly underestimates than observed discharge. The poor performance of hydrological models using satellite precipitation product has been noticed by a various researcher (Bajracharya et al., 2017). There are common views on correction of high-resolution satellite rainfall estimates before using into an operational hydrological model (Thiemig et al., 2013). The TRMM and MSWEP after bias correction may be used for flood modeling and Aphrodite can be used for water balance estimation where there is the unavailability of rain gauge, complex geographical condition and place where the establishment of rain gauge is not economically feasible. The validation of the remote sensing products is only possible if the resolution of product able to quantify the range of spatial variability (Andermann *et. al*, 2011). Precise and accurate satellite-derived data are important for documenting and verifying historical incidents such as landslide, droughts and flood event that take place in the complex terrain of an area like country Nepal in order to save life and property. Reliable satellite products are the basis for active climatological monitoring of precipitation which is very much useful across the distributed population of extreme terrain.

6.2 Recommendations

In this study, there are many positive aspects of the study. However, there are some limitations which should be solved in future research and learning. Following are a recommendation for further study.

1. For Tibetan part, the Aphrodite product is used as rainfall input for the model calibration. So, it is recommended to use gauge data from Tibetan part.
2. As the density of rainfall station decreased with increasing elevation so more rainfall station should be established at high elevation mountain and Himalayan part. So it is recommended to establish gauge station in such geographical area for proper representation of rainfall from the whole basin. Otherwise, the validation of result may not be reliable.
3. While developing soil parameter, the all soil depth is taken 80 cm. But in reality, such condition is not possible. So it is very much important to develop the soil depth mapping or some sample of soil can be collected to represent real field condition.
4. Satellite precipitation with higher spatial and temporal resolution should be chosen to get a better result.
5. Uncertainty in the model is always the question mark in the validation of result. So. In coming future the uncertainty should be analyzed for a better result.
6. Data quality and scarcity is the major drawback in the research. Some of the stations have the data gap continuously more than 5 years. The interpolation and extrapolation in RBIS platform aren't always reliable and mayn't represent actual field condition. In some year there is a huge difference in observed and simulated discharge. It may have a chance of error in discharge measurement. So data collecting agencies Department of hydrology and meteorology (DHM) should update the existing method of rating curve analysis to make the discharge data more reliable.
7. Other available precipitation products should be evaluated in order to conclude the best product for the study area.
8. In the literature review, it was revealed the orography have higher effect in precipitation estimation especially in mountainous, Himalayan and high elevation area. So such factor should be quantified to correct the bias error of precipitation estimation.
9. Improvement in the satellite orbits and sensor drift may be an interesting topic in advance research to ensure a quality of precipitation products.

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Annex

Annex 1: Rainfall station considered in study area

SNO	INDEX	STATION	X	Y	Elevation
1	1006	Gumthang	85.87	27.87	2000
2	1008	Nawalpur	85.62	27.80	1592
3	1016	Sarmathang	85.60	27.95	2625
4	1020	Mandan	85.65	27.70	1365
5	1024	Dhulikhel	85.55	27.62	1552
6	1027	Bahrabise	85.90	27.78	1220
7	1038	Dhunibesi	85.18	27.72	1085
8	1103	Jiri	86.23	27.63	2003
9	1104	Melung	86.05	27.52	1536
10	1107	Sindhuligadhi	85.97	27.28	1463
11	1108	Bahuntulpung	86.17	27.18	1417
12	1112	Chisapani Bazar	86.17	26.92	165
13	1115	Nepalthok	85.82	27.45	1098
14	1118	Manusmara	85.42	26.88	100
15	1121	Karmaiya	85.47	27.12	131
16	1202	Chaurikhark	86.72	27.70	2619
17	1204	Aisealukhark	86.75	27.35	2143
18	1206	Okhaldhunga	86.50	27.32	1720
19	1212	Phatepur	86.93	26.73	100
20	1213	Uhayapur Gadhi	86.52	26.93	1175
21	1215	Lahan	86.43	26.73	138
22	1219	Salleri	86.58	27.50	2378
23	1223	Rajbiraj	86.75	26.55	91
24	1224	Sirwa	86.38	27.55	1662
25	1301	Num	87.28	27.55	1497
26	1303	Chainpur	87.33	27.28	1329
27	1304	Pakhribas	87.28	27.05	1680
28	1305	Leguwa Ghat	87.28	27.13	412
29	1307	Dhankuta	87.35	26.98	1445
30	1308	Mulghat	87.33	26.93	365
31	1311	Dharanbazar	87.28	26.82	444
32	1312	Haraincha	87.38	26.62	152
33	1314	Terhathum	87.55	27.13	1633
34	1316	Chatara	87.17	26.82	183
35	1319	Biratnagar Airport	87.27	26.48	72

Continue of Annex 1

SNO	INDEX	STATION	X	Y	Elevation
36	1320	Tarahara	87.27	26.70	200
37	1325	Dingla	87.15	27.37	1190
38	1403	Lungthung	87.78	27.55	1780
39	1405	Taplejung	87.67	27.35	1732
40	1406	Memengjagat	87.93	27.20	1830
41	1407	Ilam Tea Estate	87.90	26.92	1300
42	1409	Anarmani Birta	87.98	26.63	122
43	1416	Kanyam Tea Estate	88.07	26.87	1678
44	10001	T1	85.66	28.99	4762
45	10002	T2	86.10	28.98	5462
46	10003	T3	86.10	28.68	4761
47	10004	T4	85.67	28.69	4807
48	10005	T5	85.69	28.40	6149
49	10006	T6	86.11	28.10	4785
50	10007	T7	86.11	28.40	4564
51	10008	T8	86.53	28.69	5088
52	10009	T9	86.53	29.00	5192
53	10010	T10	86.54	28.39	5341
54	10011	T11	86.54	28.09	5204
55	10012	T12	86.97	28.09	6450
56	10013	T13	86.97	28.40	4485
57	10014	T14	86.97	28.69	4606
58	10015	T15	87.39	28.69	5616
59	10016	T16	87.41	28.40	4829
60	10017	T17	87.40	28.10	4957
61	10018	T18	87.82	28.08	5484
62	10019	T19	87.82	28.39	4372
63	10020	T20	87.83	28.70	4509
64	10021	T21	88.27	28.68	5514
65	10022	T22	88.27	28.38	4461
66	10023	T23	88.25	28.08	4987
67	10024	T24	88.69	28.09	5303
68	10025	T25	88.70	28.39	4979

Source: (DHM, 2017 and Aphrodite, 2017)

Annex 2: Cumulative data gap of rainfall station

SNO	INDEX	STATION	X	Y	Elevation	Data Gap
1	1303	Chainpur	87.33	27.28	1329	0
2	1311	Dharanbazar	87.28	26.82	444	0
3	1319	Biratnagar Airport	87.27	26.48	72	0
4	1403	Lungthung	87.78	27.55	1780	0
5	1038	Dhunibesi	85.18	27.72	1085	31
6	1305	Leguwa Ghat	87.28	27.13	412	43
7	1206	Okhaldhunga	86.50	27.32	1720	79
8	1115	Nepalthok	85.82	27.45	1098	93
9	1320	Tarahara	87.27	26.70	200	93
10	1316	Chatara	87.17	26.82	183	106
11	1219	Salleri	86.58	27.50	2378	121
12	1308	Mulghat	87.33	26.93	365	121
13	1314	Terhathum	87.55	27.13	1633	122
14	1307	Dhankuta	87.35	26.98	1445	123
15	1103	Jiri	86.23	27.63	2003	134
16	1121	Karmaiya	85.47	27.12	131	152
17	1118	Manusmara	85.42	26.88	100	153
18	1325	Dingla	87.15	27.37	1190	179
19	1304	Pakhribas	87.28	27.05	1680	214
20	1024	Dhulikhel	85.55	27.62	1552	274
21	1108	Bahuntipung	86.17	27.18	1417	303
22	1027	Bahrabise	85.90	27.78	1220	361
23	1204	Aisealukhark	86.75	27.35	2143	365
24	1405	Taplejung	87.67	27.35	1732	365
25	1006	Gumthang	85.87	27.87	2000	388
26	1409	Anarmani Birta	87.98	26.63	122	394
27	1223	Rajbiraj	86.75	26.55	91	487
28	1212	Phatepur	86.93	26.73	100	488
29	1016	Sarmathang	85.60	27.95	2625	549
30	1008	Nawalpur	85.62	27.80	1592	600
31	1112	Chisapani Bazar	86.17	26.92	165	643
32	1301	Num	87.28	27.55	1497	709
33	1213	Uhayapur Gadhi	86.52	26.93	1175	717
34	1104	Melung	86.05	27.52	1536	803
35	1416	Kanyam Tea Estate	88.07	26.87	1678	847
36	1312	Haraincha	87.38	26.62	152	916

Continue of Annex 2

SNO	INDEX	STATION	X	Y	Elevation	Data Gap
37	1202	Chaurikhark	86.72	27.70	2619	943
38	1407	Ilam Tea Estate	87.90	26.92	1300	962
39	1406	Memengjagat	87.93	27.20	1830	1095
40	1224	Sirwa	86.38	27.55	1662	1203
41	1107	Sindhuligadhi	85.97	27.28	1463	1217
42	1020	Mandan	85.65	27.70	1365	1366
43	1215	Lahan	86.43	26.73	138	1412

Annex 3: Unit of different input dataset

Name	description	unit
ahum.dat	absolute humidity	g/cm ³
orun.dat	measured flow passage at the runoff	m ³ /s
rain.dat	measured amount of precipitation	mm
rhum.dat	relative humidity	%
sunh.dat	sunshine duration	h
tmax.dat	maximum temperature	°C
tmean.dat	mean air temperature	°C
tmin.dat	minimum temperature	°C
wind.dat	wind speed	m/s

Annex 4: Soil parameters for the Koshi basin

ID	depth	kf_min	depth_min	kf_max	cap_rise	aircap	fc_sum	fc_1	fc_2	fc_3	fc_4	fc_5	fc_6	fc_7	fc_8	fc_9
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
-9999	-9999	-9999	-9999	-9999	1	-9999	-9999	-9999	-9999	-9999	-9999	-9999	-9999	-9999	-9999	-9999
n/a	cm	m/d	m	m/d	0/1	mm	mm	mm/dm	mm/dm	mm/dm	mm/dm	mm/dm	mm/dm	mm/dm	mm/dm	mm/dm
1	80	1	0.5	2	0	47.63	224.165	27.72	27.905	28.09	28.09	28.09	28.09	28.09	28.09	0
2	80	1	0.5	2	0	48.43	223.78	26.9	27.56	28.22	28.22	28.22	28.22	28.22	28.22	0
3	80	1	0.5	2	0	40.135	232.025	30.1	29.425	28.75	28.75	28.75	28.75	28.75	28.75	0
4	80	1	0.5	2	0	39.29	235.385	29.35	29.395	29.44	29.44	29.44	29.44	29.44	29.44	0
5	80	1	0.5	2	0	43.52	228.285	29.47	28.895	28.32	28.32	28.32	28.32	28.32	28.32	0
6	80	1	0.5	2	0	29.665	247.99	30.82	30.93	31.04	31.04	31.04	31.04	31.04	31.04	0
7	80	1	0.5	2	0	41.76	230.72	28.84	28.84	28.84	28.84	28.84	28.84	28.84	28.84	0
8	80	1	0.5	2	0	121.23	144.335	17.66	17.895	18.13	18.13	18.13	18.13	18.13	18.13	0
9	80	1	0.5	2	0	40.31	274.43	32.89	33.76	34.63	34.63	34.63	34.63	34.63	34.63	0
10	80	1	0.5	2	0	40.29	232.06	29.56	29.22	28.88	28.88	28.88	28.88	28.88	28.88	0
11	80	1	0.5	2	0	1	8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
12	80	1	0.5	2	0	54.265	224.475	20.82	25.275	29.73	29.73	29.73	29.73	29.73	29.73	0
13	80	1	0.5	2	0	24.02	275.89	34.34	34.43	34.52	34.52	34.52	34.52	34.52	34.52	0
14	80	1	0.5	2	0	21.955	257.49	32.43	32.28	32.13	32.13	32.13	32.13	32.13	32.13	0
15	80	1	0.5	2	0	174.32	88.08	11.01	11.01	11.01	11.01	11.01	11.01	11.01	11.01	0
16	80	1	0.5	2	0	174.32	88.08	11.01	11.01	11.01	11.01	11.01	11.01	11.01	11.01	0
17	80	1	0.5	2	0	166.34	92.94	10.48	11.18	11.88	11.88	11.88	11.88	11.88	11.88	0
18	80	1	0.5	2	0	36.86	236.11	30.31	29.82	29.33	29.33	29.33	29.33	29.33	29.33	0
19	80	1	0.5	2	0	38.96	233.92	29.24	29.24	29.24	29.24	29.24	29.24	29.24	29.24	0
20	80	1	0.5	2	0	50.085	219.61	28.28	27.77	27.26	27.26	27.26	27.26	27.26	27.26	0
21	80	1	0.5	2	0	35.74	239.52	30.46	30.14	29.82	29.82	29.82	29.82	29.82	29.82	0
22	80	1	0.5	2	0	25.325	252.88	31.48	31.56	31.64	31.64	31.64	31.64	31.64	31.64	0
23	80	1	0.5	2	0	35.16	251.44	31.3	31.38	31.46	31.46	31.46	31.46	31.46	31.46	0
24	80	1	0.5	2	0	43.575	261.005	34.08	33.185	32.29	32.29	32.29	32.29	32.29	32.29	0
25	80	1	0.5	2	0	26.99	255.99	32.34	32.13	31.92	31.92	31.92	31.92	31.92	31.92	0

Continue of Annex 4

ID	depth	kf_min	depth_min	kf_max	cap_rise	aircap	fc_sum	fc_1	fc_2	fc_3	fc_4	fc_5	fc_6	fc_7	fc_8	fc_9
26	80	1	0.5	2	0	63.04	227.36	28.42	28.42	28.42	28.42	28.42	28.42	28.42	28.42	0
27	80	1	0.5	2	0	18.96	261.92	32.74	32.74	32.74	32.74	32.74	32.74	32.74	32.74	0
28	80	1	0.5	2	0	22.465	256.68	31.89	32.01	32.13	32.13	32.13	32.13	32.13	32.13	0
29	80	1	0.5	2	0	115.04	166.56	20.82	20.82	20.82	20.82	20.82	20.82	20.82	20.82	0
30	80	1	0.5	2	0	43.68	227.36	28.42	28.42	28.42	28.42	28.42	28.42	28.42	28.42	0
31	80	1	0.5	2	0	26.545	252.6	31.38	31.5	31.62	31.62	31.62	31.62	31.62	31.62	0
32	80	1	0.5	2	0	33.455	245.915	28.44	29.855	31.27	31.27	31.27	31.27	31.27	31.27	0
33	80	1	0.5	2	0	24.96	251.84	31.48	31.48	31.48	31.48	31.48	31.48	31.48	31.48	0
34	80	1	0.5	2	0	40.655	233.24	29.35	29.23	29.11	29.11	29.11	29.11	29.11	29.11	0
35	80	1	0.5	2	0	1	8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0

Source: (FAO/IIASA/ISRIC/ISSCAS/JRC, 2012)

Soil parameter description

Parameter	Description
SID	soil type ID
depth	soil depth
kf_min	minimum permeability coefficient
depth_min	depth of the horizon above the horizon with the smallest permeability coefficient
kf_max	maximum permeability coefficient
cap_rise	Boolean variable, that allows (1) or restricts (0) capillary ascension
aircap	air capacity (equivalent to large pore storage (LPS))
fc_sum	usable field capacity (equivalent to middle pore storage (MPS))
fc_1 ...22	usable field capacity per decimeter of profile depth

Annex 5: Land use parameters for the Koshi basin

LID	description	albedo	RSC_0_1	RSC_0_2	RS_C0_3	RS_C0_4	RSC_0_5	RSC_0_6	RSC_0_7	RS_C0_8	RS_C0_9	RS_C0_10	RS_C0_11	RSC_0_12	LAI_d1	LAI_d2	LAI_d3	LAI_d4	effHeight_d1	effHeight_d2	effHeight_d3	effHeight_d4	rootDepth	sealedGrade
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
-9999	-9999	100	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	100	100	100	100	50	50	50	50	50	1
n/a	n/a	%	s/m	s/m	s/m	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	m	m	m	m	dm	n/a									
15	grassland	0.2	80	80	70	60	40	45	45	45	50	60	80	80	0.17	3.28	3.28	0	1	1	1	1	2	0
13	coniferous forest	0.14	70	70	60	55	45	45	45	45	50	65	70	70	3.5	4.95	4.95	3.75	7	10	10	7.5	3.5	0
14	deciduous forest	0.14	80	80	70	65	55	55	55	55	60	75	80	80	0.25	4.95	4.95	3.75	3.5	5.7	5.7	4.5	3.5	0
12	mixed forest	0.14	75	75	65	60	50	50	50	50	55	70	75	75	0.25	4.75	4.75	3.75	4.5	5.7	5.7	4.5	3.5	0
11	agriculture land	0.16	80	80	75	65	45	50	50	50	50	65	80	80	0.27	3.2	3.2	1	0.15	1.9	1.9	1.5	1.8	0
16	shrubland	0.14	80	80	70	60	50	50	50	55	55	70	80	80	1.2	5.7	5.7	1.2	1.5	2.5	2.5	1.5	2.1	0
17	bareland/per.snow	0.2	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.3
18	waterbodies	0.21	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
19	rockyMountains	0.21	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.8
222	glaciers	0.16	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0

Source: (adapted from Nepal (2012) and Bontemps et al. (2013))

Land use parameter description

Parameter	Description
LID	land use ID
Albedo	albedo in %
RSC0_1 to RSC0_12	minimum surface resistance for water-saturated soil in January to December
LAI_d1	leaf area index (LAI) at the beginning of the vegetation period (Jan-Mar)
LAI_d4	leaf area index (LAI) at the end of the vegetation period (Oct-Dec)
effHeight_d1	effective vegetation height at the beginning of the vegetation period (Jan-Mar)
effHeight_d4	effective vegetation height at the end of the vegetation period (Oct-Dec)
rootDepth	root depth
sealedGrade	sealed grade of surface

Annex 6: Geological parameter of Koshi basin

GID	RG1_max	RG2_max	RG1_k	RG2_k	RG1_active
1	0	0	0	0	0
-9999	-9999	-9999	-9999	-9999	1
n/a	mm	mm	d	d	n/a
1	0	0	0	0	0
2	200	825	50	572	1
3	300	1050	50	677	1
4	180	700	50	500	1

Source: (adapted from Nepal (2012) and Schwarze (1999))

Where GID 1 is Glacier part

GID 2 is Higher Himalaya

GID3 is Mountain and Siwalik

GID4 is Tibetan part

Geological parameter description

GID	hydro-geology ID	Unit
RG1_max	maximum storage capacity of the upper ground-water reservoir	mm/day
RG2_max	maximum storage capacity of the lower ground-water reservoir	mm/day
RG1_k	storage coefficient of the upper ground-water reservoir	
RG2_k	storage coefficient of the lower ground-water reservoir	

Annex 7: Calibration parameter for J2000 modelling of different satellite based precipitation products under method II

Parameters	Descriptions	TRMM	Aphrodite	MSWEP	CMORPH
PRECIP DISTRIBUTION					
Trs	base temperature	0	0	0	0
Interception Module					
a_rain	interception storage for rain	1	1	1	1
a_snow	interception storage for snow	1.28	1.28	1.28	1.28
SNOW MODULE					
snowCritDens	critical density of Snow	0.381	0.381	0.381	0.381
snowColdContent (ccf_factor)	cold content of snow pack	0.0012	0.0012	0.0012	0.0012
baseTemp	threshold temperature for snowmelt	0	0	0	0
t_factor	melt factor by sensible heat	2.84	2.84	1.26	4.84
r_factor	melt factor by liquid precipitation	0.21	0.21	0.35	1.21
g_factor	melt factor by soil heat flow	3.73	3.73	0.24	4.73
GLACIER MODULE					
meltFactorIce	melt factor for ice melt	2.5	5	0.1	4.5
alphaIce	radiation melt factor for ice	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2
kIce	routing co-efficient for ice melt	10	10	10	10
kSnow	routing co-efficient for snowmelt	5	5	5	5
kRain	routing co-efficient for rain runoff	5	5	5	5
debrisFactor	debris factor for ice melt	3	1	8	1
tbase	threshold temperature for snowmelt	-1	-1	-1	-1
SOIL MODULE					
soilMaxDPS	maximum depression storage	1	1	10	1
soilLinRed	linear reduction co-efficient for AET	0.1	1	0.01	10
soilMaxInfSummer	maximum infiltration in summer	20	10	195	18
soilMaxInfWinter	maximum infiltration in winter	140	15	200	20
soilMaxInfSnow	maximum infiltration in snow cover areas	10	5	150	10
soilImpGT80	infiltration for areas greater than 80% sealing	0.2	0.2	0.6	0.2
soilImpLT80	infiltration for areas lesser than 80% sealing	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.3
SoilDistMPSLPS	MPS-LPS distribution coefficient	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.27
SoilDiffMPSLPS	MPS-LPS diffusion coefficient	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
soilOutLPS	outflow coefficient for LPS	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
soilLatVertLPS	lateral vertical distribution coefficient	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
soilMaxPerc	maximum percolation rate to groundwater	10	10	10	10
soilConcRD1Flood	recession coefficient for flood event	1	1.3	2.5	1
soilConcRD1Floodthreshold	threshold value for soilConcRD1Flood	1500	300	1500	100
soilConcRD1	recession coefficient for overland flow	2	3	3	1.2
soilConcRD2	recession coefficient for Interflow	4	6	4	1.5

Continue of Annex 7

Parameters	Descriptions	TRMM	Aphrodite	MSWEP	CMORPH
GROUNDWATER MODULE					
gwRG1RG2dist	RG1-RG2 distribution coefficient	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1
gwRG1Fact	adaptation for RG1 flow	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
gwRG2Fact	adaptation for RG2 flow	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
gwCapRise	capillary rise coefficient	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
REACH ROUTING					
flowRouteTA	flood routing coefficient	2	8	1.8	25

(Note: The red letter represent most sensitive parameter, blue letter denote medium sensitive parameter and black letter represent less sensitive parameter)

Declaration in lieu of oath

By

“Rajesh Khatakho”

This is to confirm my Master’s Thesis was independently composed/authored by myself, using solely the referred sources and support.

I additionally assert that this Thesis has not been part of another examination process.

Place and Date

Signature